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CENTER FOR BIOLOGICS EVALUATION AND RESEARCH

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VACCINES AND RELATED BIOLOGICAL PRODUCTS ADVISORY
COMMITTEE

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OPEN SESSION

THURSDAY
NOVEMBER 29, 2001

The Advisory Committee in Versailles Room I and II in the Holiday Inn Bethesda, 8120 Wisconsin Avenue, Rockville, Maryland, at 8:30 a.m., Dr. Robert S. Daum, Chair, presiding.

PRESENT:

ROBERT S. DAUM, M.D.	Chair
MICHAEL D. DECKER, M.D., M.P.H.	Member
WALTER L. FAGGETT, M.D.	Member
BARBARA LOE FISHER	Member
JUDITH D. GOLDBERG, Sc.D.	Member
DIANE E. GRIFFIN, M.D.	Member
SAMUEL L. KATZ, M.D.	Member
KWANG SIK KIM, M.D.	Member
STEVE KOHL, M.D.	Member
PETER PALESE, Ph.D.	Member
DIXIE E. SNIDER, JR., M.D., M.P.J.	Member
JUAN FELIX, M.D.	Invited Participant
THOMAS FLEMING, Ph.D.	Invited Participant
MICHAEL GREENE, M.D.	Invited Participant
PAMELA McINNES, DDS.	Invited Participant
MARTIN MYERS, M.D.	Invited Participant
DENNIS O'CONNOR, M.D.	Invited Participant
SONIA PAGLIUSI, Ph.D.	Invited Participant
WILLIAM REEVES, M.D.	Invited Participant
ELLEN SHEETS, M.D.	Invited Participant
ELIZABETH UNGER, M.D., Ph.D.	Invited Participant
EDWARD WILKINSON, M.D.	Invited Participant

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Session 4

Call to Order, Dr. Robert S. Daum3

Committee Discussion and Recommendations6

Session 5

Briefing on Activities in the Laboratory of Bacterial
Toxins

Organizational Structure and Overview of Research and
Regulatory Responsibilities in the Division of Bacterial,
Parasitic and Allergenic Products, Dr. Richard Walker,
FDA153

Organizational Structure and Overview of Regulatory
Responsibilities in the Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins,
Dr. Willie Vann, FDA162

Description of Research Activities, Dr. Willie Vann, FDA
.....170

Description of Research Activities, Dr. Michael Schmitt,
FDA181

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P-R-O-C-E-E-D-I-N-G-S

8:33 a.m.

DR. DAUM: Good morning. A couple of announcements before we get down to business, so to speak.

First, for panel and committee members there are bins up in front for paper that you've carried her laboriously and don't wish to carry home. Please use them.

Secondly, for panel members Denise and Rosana are, as always, kind enough to help us arrange transportation to airports or other destinations. For panel members at the table, please feel free to ask them to help you should you need.

Thirdly, I would like to call on Bill Freas -- where is he? There he is -- to make the briefest of announcements.

DR. FREAS: Thank you, Dr. Daum. I would just like to announcement that at the end of the meeting, whenever that is, that will be at the end of the closed session, we will have a short retirement ceremony for Nancy Cherry.

Let me just take two words to comment quickly on Nancy's distinguished 10-year career at FDA. Committee members know that she's always working late at night which seems to be the norm. But she's also here at this meetings long before I even roll out of bed in

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1 the morning to make sure everything is set. We
2 really are appreciative of all the hard work that she
3 has been doing. On behalf of CBER and her colleagues,
4 we're going to have a little cake. We invite the public.

5 We invite everybody on the committee to share this little
6 party with us.

7 This is the unofficial requirement party just
8 because she won't officially retire until January 3rd
9 but we wanted to have something and to celebrate her
10 distinguished career here while the committee members
11 were here. Thank you.

12 MS. CHERRY: Thank you. I was trying to keep
13 it quiet until the end of the day but I appreciate it.

14 Thank you, Bill, Bob, everyone.

15 DR. DAUM: And for committee members and
16 temporary voting members, guests at the table, you've
17 got about three hours to talk her out of it. We're hoping
18 to be able to apply pressure.

19 I can tell you in a short time as chairman of
20 this committee that no Nancy, no meeting. It's just as
21 simple as that. I'm incredibly grateful for the support
22 and constant vigilance that she provides. Jabs in the
23 elbow notwithstanding, it's been a great collaboration.

24 The strategy for this morning that I would like
25 to propose to the panel is to have some free discussion

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1 first to look at issues that people felt were hanging
2 from yesterday to raise issues that either we need more
3 clarification or that you would just like to hear some
4 committee discussion with regard to the questions only
5 one of which currently fits on the screen but is up there
6 for your viewing pleasure.

7 Once we get a sense of the fact that we are
8 sort of starting to be repetitive and not raising crisp
9 new issues, then I would like to take stock to address
10 the question directly. At that point we may have heard
11 from half or two-thirds of the panel on the issue but
12 we will ask every member, regular and temporary, to
13 comment directly on the question.

14 So with that sort of introduction, I've rigged
15 things a little bit with an issue that was on my mind
16 and would like to ask Marty Myers to initiate the first
17 issue. It doesn't mean that we have to stay fixated on
18 this issued. We can wander around on anything the
19 committee's pleasure. Then we will eventually reach a
20 point where we start focusing directly on the question.

21 Marty, you were kind enough to accept this
22 gauntlet from me and would you start us off.

23 DR. MYERS: I thought we would talk around the
24 very important issue that I remain a bit confused about.

25 I would like to ask a question to the people who are

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1 experts in this.

2 When we were talking about the contextual
3 issues yesterday, the specific issue really didn't get
4 laid flatly on the table so I would like to put it flatly
5 on the table.

6 Specifically in Dr. Schiffman's presentation,
7 at least as I understood it, he implied that persistent
8 infection of a year's duration would, in fact, imply that
9 there was a standard of care that would be implied.
10 Somebody with persistent infection might, in fact,
11 require therapy.

12 As I look at the data, it seemed to me that
13 places a woman at very high risk of high-grade disease
14 and might require long-term close supervision. If, in
15 fact, it implies a standard of care of treatment, then,
16 in fact, the experts in the field have already defined
17 this as a surrogate. It makes it very difficult to
18 consider using CIN 2, CIN 3, for example, a high-grade
19 disease, as an endpoint because everybody will have had
20 intervention before.

21 My question is really to those people who
22 understanding the management of these individuals. If
23 a person has a persistent infection, does that imply a
24 specific therapeutic intervention or is that a
25 supervision? I think that's a critical issue.

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1 DR. DAUM: I think so, too, and I'm glad people
2 want to respond. Let's start with Dixie and then Drs.
3 Wilkinson and Felix.

4 DR. SNIDER: Actually, I want to elaborate
5 because I had an opportunity to talk with Dr. Schiffman
6 more about that particular issue which was troubling me
7 greatly as well.

8 If I understood him correctly, during his
9 presentation he was telling us that the optimal time
10 wasn't really known but that, in his opinion, it was
11 somewhere between one and two years.

12 The reason he -- if he's in the audience,
13 perhaps he should speak. The reason he came up with one
14 year was not because of the data that he has in hand,
15 but because he has been receiving lots of pressure from
16 organizations who feel compelled given the current body
17 of knowledge to come up with some definition of what
18 recurrent infection is. Persistent. I'm sorry. What
19 persistent infection is. For lack of the more
20 extensive data from his study not being available, not
21 yet being analyzed, the one year is somewhat arbitrary
22 in terms of his personal recommendation. There is some
23 concern on his part that a number of organizations,
24 standard settings, professional organizations may take
25 that number and do exactly what Marty is implying.

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1 It's just a little elaboration, I think
2 accurate, from Mark about how this transpired. Then I,
3 too, would like to hear what some experts think about
4 that particular situation.

5 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much. Let's
6 continue with Dr. Wilkinson, then Dr. Felix, and Dr.
7 Sheets.

8 DR. WILKINSON: I would just like to address
9 the issue of persistent viral shedding. The ASCCP
10 guidelines that were developed, these are guidelines not
11 standard of care that were developed in September of this
12 year, had access to National Cancer Institute data that
13 is yet unpublished relevant to persistent viral shedding
14 which Dr. Schiffman alluded to yesterday.

15 First, let me say that viral shedding in and
16 of itself would not be an indication for treatment but
17 it may be an indication for reevaluation of the patient
18 by colposcopy.

19 In that setting under the guidelines, and these
20 are submitted at this point, but basically an acceptable
21 -- not recommended but an acceptable statement from the
22 guidelines is that an option in follow-up of women with
23 LSIL, where an option has been chosen to follow the patient
24 rather than treat the patient, the recommendation is
25 colposcopy first, biopsy any visible lesions, with mild

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1 dysplasia the option would be that you could follow the
2 patient.

3 There's only a couple of exceptions.
4 Adolescents and elderly women are some exceptions. The
5 point being that at the end of a year or at some point,
6 possibly two years, your option would be that as an
7 acceptable option to do HPV testing for high-risk HPV
8 type.

9 If the HPV is positive at that point, you then
10 go to colposcopy, an examination of the patient. If we
11 have persistent viral shedding, there is very good
12 evidence that NCI presented that your patient probably
13 has a persistent lesion.

14 I would emphasize this is an acceptable option
15 and it's not the standard of care that these guidelines
16 -- ASCCP does not establish standard of care. American
17 College of OB/GYN does so that is something that can looked
18 at at that point.

19 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Wilkinson.

20 Dr. Felix, then Dr. Sheets, and Dr. O'Connor.

21 DR. FELIX: I'll be brief because Dr. Wilkinson
22 basically stated all the facts. I'll just add that I
23 know of no organization, nor of any expert panel that
24 will recommend therapy based on viral information. They
25 will recommend examination of the patient but never

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1 therapy just based on viral shedding.

2 Clearly not only not the standard of care of,
3 in fact, it's never been recommended officially to
4 actually perform therapy due to viral shedding in itself.

5 Just evaluation and diagnosis.

6 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

7 Dr. Sheets.

8 DR. SHEETS: I think there are actually two
9 issues on the table when Dr. Schiffman was talking. I
10 think they have been somewhat blurred in terms of their
11 overlap here. One is the issue of what represents viral
12 persistence in and of itself separate from a side logic
13 abnormality.

14 I think there is fairly good data to show that
15 persistence of viral shedding six months apart for a year,
16 or maybe two years, is certainly a person who
17 cytologically normal at that time has great risk for the
18 development of a lesion in the future.

19 That's a separate issue from people who have
20 -- women who have a cytologic abnormality and are
21 concurrently a high-risk viral type. Then we go and
22 subsequently a year later look for presence of that viral
23 type as a surrogate of the lesion being still present
24 on the cervix that gave rise to that cytologic
25 abnormality.

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1 That is a different scenario. That is not what
2 is being discussed as a surrogate marker for failure of
3 the vaccine in this mortality or this current discussion.

4 Those women who had cytologic abnormalities
5 who had high-risk viral shedding at the incipient visit
6 for vaccine therapy would not accrue in a trial. Correct?

7 So that is a different scenario than someone who is
8 shedding the virus at some point in the future with or
9 without a cytologic abnormality.

10 I think that when Dr. Schiffman was talking
11 about using viral shedding, as Dr. Felix pointed out,
12 as a point for therapy or further evaluation by
13 colposcopy, that was in the context of cytologic
14 abnormality as the American Society of Colposcopy and
15 Cervical Pathology guidelines indicate for LSIL at this
16 point so there are two different categories.

17 DR. DAUM: Can we press you a little bit, or
18 can I press you a little bit because that's very helpful.

19 The only circumstances is it true -- is what I'm saying
20 true that the only circumstances that someone would seek
21 viral shedding in a totally asymptomatic woman with no
22 lesions is for research purposes or documentation
23 purposes? There's no medical care issue there at all.

24 DR. SHEETS: Currently in 2001 there is no
25 medical indication for a cytologically normal woman to

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1 be tested for HPV from a medical point of view. There
2 are no guidelines that indicate to do that. This would
3 be a research setting at this point in time.

4 DR. DAUM: Do I hear in the first thing you
5 said, though, is there talk or plans of incorporating
6 routine screening?

7 DR. SHEETS: I think there certainly are a body
8 of people in this country who think that HPV could be
9 a surrogate for cytologic evaluation of woman, but that
10 data is not mature for the United States.

11 DR. DAUM: Not about to happen.

12 DR. SHEETS: Not about to happen.

13 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much. That's very
14 helpful.

15 Dr. O'Connor.

16 DR. O'CONNOR: I thought about this yesterday
17 and had some discussion with a number of people and what
18 I will give you are what I gleaned from discussions and
19 basically my opinions.

20 Most papilloma virus infections regress over
21 time. Those that don't are the infections that can result
22 in high-grade dysplasia or worse. The interval before
23 persistence become clinically significant is unknown but
24 it is probably one to two years.

25 We do not know what factors are necessary for

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1 persistence but why only certain HPV DNA types are
2 associated with significant disease. Although
3 persistence carries an increased risk of significant
4 disease, there's no evidence that these woman should be
5 prophylactically treated because what are you treating?

6 I don't think there is enough evidence to
7 suggest to me that woman with persistent unexplained
8 oncogenic HPV have an inordinately high risk of finding
9 underlying high-grade CIN being defined as CIN 2 and 3.

10
11 I feel that based on what I've heard there is,
12 however, enough evidence to suggest that persistent
13 oncogenic HPV has enough of a risk for eventually finding
14 an underlying CIN of any grade that you can it a vaccine
15 failure. That's as far as I would take it

16 DR. DAUM: Go ahead, Dr. Sheets.

17 DR. SHEETS: I think to elaborate on what Dr.
18 O'Connor is saying is that when one thinks of surrogate
19 endpoints for this vaccine therapy using approximate
20 surrogate such as HPV, high-risk oncogenic type
21 positivity, or persistence of that presence as a point
22 of failure for the vaccine will slightly artificially
23 increase the efficacy or apparent efficacy of the vaccine
24 since some of these HPV infections by high-risk oncogenic
25 types are transient and clinically irrelevant, not

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1 important.

2 Even some in the face of cytologic slight
3 abnormalities we know will regress over time. Using a
4 marker that is more approximate rather than more distal
5 from the actual invasive cervical cancer rather than more
6 approximate will make the vaccine efficacy appear to be
7 higher.

8 That is neither here nor there to a certain
9 extent, but if one thinks about the scenario of what we're
10 trying to treat which is either high-risk precursors or
11 invasive cancer, we have to remember that the clientele
12 that we are treating with the vaccine are at least a decade
13 younger than the average age of onset of high-risk
14 precursor lesions and certainly much younger than the
15 incident age of invasive disease.

16 The question arises here as to what the efficacy
17 of the vaccine will be for those lesions later on a decade
18 or so later. Problems with this that aren't part of the
19 discussion today in the background that one has to keep
20 in mind are that we know very little about the induction
21 of mucosal immunity as compared to serologic markers of
22 immunity induced by a vaccine.

23 We don't know whether memory in the mucosal
24 immune system will be the same as the surrogate markers
25 and serum for systemic infections. Ten to 15 years later

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1 when that 18 and 20-year-old is at greatest risk for the
2 development of precancer or invasive disease, will this
3 immunotherapeutic still apply? We don't know. It's
4 outside of the discussion of this.

5 But if we use a more distal marker as a surrogate
6 marker of efficacy, or even farther away from the endpoint
7 that we ultimately want to prevent, I would think that
8 is something that we have to think about in terms of
9 discussing the surrogate endpoint.

10 DR. DAUM: Does the rigor of the definition
11 of persistence matter with regard to your comments? In
12 other words, if we take a one-year period and want four
13 cultures or a two-year period and want six cultures, does
14 that matter or the comment still stands?

15 DR. SHEETS: I think all it will do is enhance
16 the apparent efficacy of the vaccine to a certain extent
17 because you will be picking up on evidence of HPV
18 positivity that may not be clinically relevant in the
19 long run.

20 DR. DAUM: Dr. Reeves.

21 DR. REEVES: I think just one of the things
22 that we are mixing some words and some concepts and you're
23 hitting on it that we are still mixing these. As I
24 understand it, CIN 2 and CIN 3, most of them, or some
25 portion of them, are part of the actual natural history

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1 of the development of cervical cancer. CIN 2 leads to
2 or results in CIN 3 in some proportion leads to or results
3 in cervical cancer.

4 The same is not true for HPV. We're mixing
5 the terms. We're often saying persistent HPV results
6 in or leads to CIN. That's, in fact, not true. It's
7 associated with it.

8 There's a rather major difference of being
9 associated within a small number of, as are all studies,
10 flawed epidemiologic studies and selected groups, some
11 in populations and some not. But an association is not
12 causal and an association does not imply anything on a
13 path or leading to or resulting in things.

14 DR. DAUM: That's helpful.

15 Dr. Felix and then Dr. Sheets. I'm sorry, Dr.
16 Kohl was first. Dr. Kohl, Felix, and Sheets. Excuse
17 me.

18 DR. KOHL: I just want to emphasize what Dr.
19 Sheets said in terms of something we really haven't talked
20 much about, although it was mentioned in the modeling
21 -- sorry, it was mentioned yesterday -- restoration of
22 protection.

23 We're talking about almost a life-long risk
24 and, in certain situations, an increasing risk over time,
25 although that seems to be possibly controversial. We

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1 heard very, very little about hypotheses of duration or
2 protection.

3 I don't remember data on duration or protection
4 and that's really a critical issue which I think could
5 accrue in a lodge or a long-term study but I'm concerned
6 whether we would see much of that in a short study with
7 a surrogate that is closer to infection versus closer
8 to CIN 2/3.

9 DR. DAUM: Thank you for raising that point.

10 We haven't talked it for a bit.

11 Dr. Felix, Dr. Sheets, Dr. Griffin.

12 DR. FELIX: I'll actually address two points
13 quickly. Dr. Kohl brings obviously a very important
14 point, duration of protection. But we have to remember
15 that if you protect a woman very early on, that may be
16 in itself even if the protection wanes an extraordinarily
17 important protection because age at first coitus is an
18 extremely important risk factor for the development of
19 cervical cancer.

20 We don't know what it is about the
21 transformation zone of a very young woman, but clearly
22 woman who start sexual activity at the age of 16 or
23 perhaps earlier have a relative risk that is much higher
24 than woman who start first coitus after 18.

25 Obviously they are sexually naive. The

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1 initial age represents a tremendous increase in the
2 relative risk. If you protect these woman at that age,
3 even if immunity wanes, there is at least theoretical
4 benefit of even those first two or three years of
5 protection in lowering the relative risk of the population
6 for acquiring basic carcinoma.

7 Immunity even of a transient, I think, is
8 something we ought to seek. Obviously it would be better
9 if it persisted but that is maybe a very important
10 parameter.

11 In response to Dr. Reeves, I think that the
12 data suggesting that CIN 2 will progress to CIN 3 will
13 progress to cervical cancer is robust. I think that
14 currently there's almost as much data in the literature
15 suggesting that persistence of high-risk viral types if
16 you do it properly will result in the same effect.

17 Perhaps not at the same rates although very,
18 very close because the rate of progression of CIN 2 is
19 about 20 some odd percent. The rate of acquisition of
20 the high-grade dysplasia from persistent HPV is around
21 26 to 28 percent also. The data is pretty robust. Both
22 of them are associations but I think they are very
23 equivalent.

24 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

25 Dr. Sheets, then Dr. Griffin and Katz.

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1 DR. SHEETS: I think there are multiple issues
2 on the table at this point in time for which we have no
3 solid data to make statements one way or the other. I
4 guess I would respectfully disagree with Dr. Felix in
5 saying that stopping an apparent infection by the
6 parameters that we have to test for that infection today
7 ultimately will definitely result in decrease invasive
8 disease in the future. I don't know that. My
9 concern is that when we look at the epidemiology of
10 invasive disease in America, we know that in the late
11 teens, early 20's that these women are at great risk for
12 oncogenic viral infection with subsequent cytologic
13 abnormalities, perhaps even CIN 2/3 which may or may not
14 be caught and treated at that point in time, but there
15 is a large amount of regression through that decade.

16 We know that in the 30's and 40's slightly more
17 mature individuals are the ones at risk for the
18 reoccurrence or reestablishment of a high-risk lesion
19 histologically that are at risk for the invasive disease
20 that we're talking about.

21 We don't know what happens in that window.
22 We don't know if the resolution spontaneously of a
23 precursor lesion in their 20's leaves them at great risk
24 for those women, those specific women for invasive
25 disease.

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1 We know epidemiologically that HPV infection
2 is the greatest risk factor for preinvasive high-risk
3 lesions and invasive disease sans sexual partners or age
4 of first intercourse, but we don't have documentation
5 of long epidemiologic studies over a long period of time
6 with no intervention what that biology might be.

7 If we add on top of that a vaccine which
8 apparently decreases the "insipid shedding of HPV
9 infection," is that the same as never being exposed or
10 having a latent state?

11 We don't know because certainly there is a great
12 deal of discussion right now in this country in mucosal
13 immunology and HPV research that indicates there may be
14 a latent phase for women who apparently were either
15 treated or regressed their lesion in their 20's
16 redeveloping that lesion later on. We just don't know
17 that data.

18 In regards to HPV persistence in the
19 development of high-risk histology later, that is well
20 documented that may occur but, again, subject in the 20's,
21 late teens and early 20's, to the same problems associated
22 with spontaneous regression and clinical relevance of
23 those lesions at that point in time. We just don't know
24 what that translates into later than the 30's and 40's.

25

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1 Some would say that CIN 2 is variable in
2 regression rate whether it exist or not. Listening to
3 Mark Schiffman talk about it maybe it's not even a lesion
4 according to him. Some of us certainly deal with it on
5 a daily basis. That's for sure. It does regress at a
6 fairly high rate compared to documented CIN 3 but that's
7 outside the venue of this discussion.

8 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

9 Drs. Griffin, Katz, and Fleming.

10 DR. GRIFFIN: I guess I just wanted to
11 reiterate one point, and that is that I think the data
12 are excellent and nobody has really challenged them, that
13 infection is a precursor -- becoming infected with one
14 of these high-risk HPV types is a precursor to developing
15 cervical carcinoma.

16 Granted we don't understand everything that's
17 happening during those 20 years before you actually
18 diagnose the disease. Therefore, it seems to me a priori
19 that if you prevent that infection, you're going to
20 prevent the cervical carcinoma.

21 Now, that doesn't mean that -- then duration
22 becomes important, for how long you're protected. I
23 don't think it means that if you use virus or infection
24 with virus as a marker for the efficacy of the vaccine
25 that you have overestimated.

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1 If you prevent infection that you've
2 overestimated the efficacy of the vaccine, what you've
3 overestimated perhaps more likely is the efficacy for
4 preventing cervical carcinoma but not the efficacy for
5 preventing infection which is usually what we're looking
6 for in a vaccine.

7 So to me the big question then becomes it would
8 be nice to understand all these things but also whether
9 HPV types will come in and now may play a more prominent
10 role, etc., in the cervical carcinoma that develops in
11 those individuals. I think preventing infection is a
12 very important goal and readout for these vaccines.

13 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

14 Drs. Katz and then Fleming.

15 DR. KATZ: I think Dr. Sheets and Dr. Griffin
16 have helped me in my thinking. We're dealing with two
17 different worlds. One of the gynecologic oncologist and
18 then those of us who think of ourselves as vaccinologists.

19 The terms have been used back and forth inappropriate
20 perhaps.

21 We're not talking about a therapeutic vaccine.

22 I assume we're talking about a prophylactic vaccine so
23 we're preventing. That's what Diane commented on. Not
24 that we're treating and applying a therapeutic
25 intervention.

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1 Although Dr. Wilkinson showed me wonderfully
2 slides yesterday, I don't know enough about what goes
3 on in the cervix. Are there lymphoid cells? Are there
4 the equivalent of M cells? What's there that provides
5 -- Ellen was talking about mucosal immunity.

6 I know a lot about the GI track and the respiratory
7 track. I don't know anything about mucosal immunity and
8 what to expect as far as local host defense is concerned.

9
10 I agree that antibodies may be fine but what
11 goes on locally may be even more important. Are there
12 lymphoid follicles? Is there trafficking of lymphocytes
13 from the cervix to other areas of where we have lymphoid
14 deposits in the body? Can you help me with that at all?

15 DR. DAUM: Dr. Wilkinson, Dr. Sheets, go ahead.

16 DR. WILKINSON: I think Dr. Sheets probably
17 has more to say on this than I do but I would say that
18 although the cervix is not considered a molt organ
19 specifically, it is richly endowed with immunologic base
20 cells.

21 Often these cells are rallied in the face of,
22 say, invasive carcinoma. You can appreciate that in many
23 settings. In certain infections such as chlamydial
24 infection it's not unusual to see aggregates of
25 lymphocytes occurring, a condition referred to as

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1 pellicular cervicitis for example.

2 The cervix also has secretory IgA and so forth.

3 It's quite a complex organ and probably should be ranked
4 among the molt organs but, in fact, is not.

5 DR. KATZ: So that leads to a little more
6 optimism about preventing infection or reinfection.

7 DR. KATZ: I want to stay focused in this issue
8 before we go on. When we go on, we'll go to Dr. Fleming
9 next. Dr. Sheets and then Dr. Felix wanted to speak to
10 this very issue.

11 DR. SHEETS: I think in published data that
12 is currently available in therapeutic vaccines we know
13 that we can give a systemic injection and have cells that
14 were destined -- T cells that were destined for mucosal
15 immunity in the cervix to be exposed to that therapeutic
16 systemically and then track back to the cervix or home
17 back.

18 We know T cell immunity does happen although
19 at a much lower rate than it would happen necessarily
20 systemically since the dose is given systemically and
21 there's a great discussion of therapeutic vaccines,
22 whether they should be given transmucosally much like
23 the GI tract, etc.

24 In terms of IgA, IGG secretion, antibody
25 secretion, there's no doubt that the cervix and its mucus

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1 has a fair amount of antibody occurring there. I am aware
2 that there are efforts to create the same type of
3 immunologic evaluation that's going on in the cirri that
4 we've heard previously prevented in closed session to
5 do transvaginally to look at that neutralizing antibody
6 from the cervical mucus.

7 There have been assays set up to do that. The
8 problem is we don't know a lot about the relationship
9 between that mucosal immune system, just as we don't know
10 about certain things in the GI tract compared to the
11 systemic.

12 We don't know about durability and we don't
13 know about level to a certain extent. This is not known.

14 This is all very new. That's what I was pointing out.

15 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

16 Dr. Felix, this issue.

17 DR. FELIX: She presented it.

18 DR. DAUM: Excellent. Let's move on then.
19 Dr. Fleming.

20 DR. FLEMING: I'd like to go back to Dr. Kohl,
21 Dr. Sheet, and Dr. Griffin who have brought up a set of
22 issues that have really been troubling me and I was
23 delighted to see that they have pursued this.

24 I guess I could cast them in the broad sense
25 of what are the durability. What is the durability of

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1 effects. What are the long-term protective effects.
2 I think of this in at least two dimensions.

3 One is what is the long-term protective effect
4 from initial HPV infection that would relate to waning
5 of immunologic response. But the other is what is the
6 long-term impact on rate of progressive disease in those
7 people who are infected.

8 Dr. Griffin, you had mentioned that the goal
9 of a vaccine is to prevent the infection. My
10 understanding is that with some vaccines the actual true
11 clinical benefit may be achieved by the impact on the
12 immune system in being able to control infection once
13 infection has occurred and what do we know about that
14 in this setting, about long-term impact on the immune
15 system.

16 I would also say that whereas the effect of
17 the vaccine may be to prevent infection or, in fact, it
18 may be to prevent the sequelae, in essence what to my
19 way of thinking really motivates any intervention is to
20 prevent something that is clinically tangible or
21 meaningful.

22 In this sense what we've really focused on is
23 cervical cancer. It seems to me entirely likely based
24 on the epidemiology that large numbers of people become
25 infected and the immune system is already capable of

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1 clearing the infection in a manner that there are no
2 sequelae.

3 What I worry about is just because there is
4 this association and it may be causal. If we provide
5 protection in 80 percent or 90 percent, it may be that
6 those are the very people whose immune system was already
7 capable of clearing the infection and, hence, preventing
8 the clinical sequelae.

9 I think this does become inherently very
10 complex and I think these issues of long-term impact are
11 important not just from the perspective of what's the
12 ability because this is a chronic risk situation. A
13 20-year-old woman will be at chronic risk for infection.

14
15 Beyond that even when you do become infected,
16 what is the overall impact of the vaccine induced immune
17 response on progressive disease, not only over the
18 short-term but also the long-term. These are a lot of
19 questions that I'm very uncertain about.

20 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Fleming.

21 Dr. Snider, then Dr. Katz.

22 DR. SNIDER: With regard to the issue --
23 continuing with the issue of preventing infection, I'm
24 still having some mixed feelings about that.

25 I mean, certainly with hepatitis B, for

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1 example, if we had said the most severe consequence of
2 hepatitis B is cirrhosis and hepatic carcinoma and we
3 want to establish a trial to show reduction in cirrhosis
4 and hepatic carcinoma, the size of that trial would have
5 been tremendous and it would have taken a very, very long
6 period of time.

7 Then the issue of preventing infections that
8 are trivial. We've dealt with this before. I mean, as
9 everybody knows, what are the numbers, Sam? I mean you
10 prevent 100 infections or is it more for every clinical
11 case that occurs.

12 Right now we don't know how to pick out who
13 is going to develop paralytic polio so we prevent a lot
14 of infections with polio virus that are going to be
15 trivial. It seems to me that -- I understand that the
16 question has to do with intended to prevent cervical
17 cancer and that this is perhaps a little bit off the mark
18 in terms of addressing the questions.

19 I guess I'm still wondering with Diane if there
20 is not enough evidence to suggest that preventing
21 infections may be something that is quite useful,
22 particularly when I hear that persistent infections are
23 likely to result in maybe not therapy but in terms of
24 additional interventions which I understand the cost of
25 those can't be -- the dollar cost can't be weighed in

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1 this discussion but performing these procedures do
2 inconvenience people. They result occasionally
3 in certain morbidity. Then dealing with some of the
4 lesions that will not apparently result in cervical cancer
5 there is not only morbidity but some low-level of
6 mortality from complications.

7 I guess all I'm trying to say is that I see
8 some societal benefits perhaps of preventing infection
9 which doesn't mean I would give up in any trial design
10 in trying to get a trial design that would also show that
11 there was a reduction in the higher grade lesions.

12 I don't think we're going to be able to use
13 -- I mean reveal right now cervical carcinoma as an
14 endpoint. I don't think ethnically that's justifiable.

15 Nevertheless, as intermediate endpoints it seems to me
16 those are very worthwhile. The question becomes whether
17 that would be sufficient information to recommend a
18 general use of the vaccine or not.

19 DR. DAUM: There are three people who want to
20 commend on what Dixie said before we go to Dr. Katz next.

21 First is Karen Goldenthal and then Tom Fleming.

22 DR. GOLDENTHAL: I just wanted to make a
23 comment about endpoints for vaccine clinical trials.
24 It seems that for most of them, in fact, there has been
25 some type of clinical case definition associated with

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1 it. I mean, for example, in polio in the Francis trial,
2 the Francis Field trial, it was really paralytic polio
3 was the endpoint.

4 With regard to hepatitis, I keep hearing about
5 hepatitis and infection was the endpoint. Certainly in
6 the FDA label it says that the vaccine is indicated for
7 the prevention of hepatitis B infection. But
8 all this talk about hepatitis B also prompted me to go
9 back and look at the smuness and don Francis efficacy
10 trials. In both of those trials there was actually --
11 they did show a prevention of infection, but they also
12 showed a prevention of hepatitis that was significant
13 between the vaccine and the placebo group. I just wanted
14 to make that point clear.

15 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

16 Dr. Fleming. We are going to stay on this very
17 point for a minute.

18 DR. KATZ: It relates to exactly what Karen
19 has said.

20 DR. DAUM: Go ahead. But Dr. Fleming is next.

21 DR. FLEMING: I yield the floor.

22 DR. KATZ: I hate to disagree with you but the
23 very data you're quoting you do not prevent infection.

24 They showed very well that with hepatitis B vaccine you
25 could have infection as shown by the fact that individuals

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1 developed anti-core antibodies.

2 DR. GOLDENTHAL: And certainly some of them
3 did.

4 DR. KATZ: So you prevent hepatitis but you
5 don't prevent infection and that's why what Tom was saying
6 I think is to me -- again, I apologize. I'm the vaccine
7 person. I'm not the gynecologist. With most vaccines
8 you do not prevent infection. You abort infection and
9 you use polio as an example.

10 If you take individuals who have been immunized
11 and don't get paralytic polio, they will shed virus.
12 If they are exposed to enough virus, they'll shed virus
13 for an abbreviated period of time in contrast to the naive
14 individual who has never seen it before. I think the
15 concept that you prevent infection is looking for too
16 stringent a criteria. You abort infection and prevent
17 persistent infection.

18 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Katz.

19 DR. KATZ: Sorry.

20 DR. DAUM: No problem. There was light shed
21 on issues.

22 DR. FLEMING: I'm delighted to hear it. I
23 concur.

24 Dixie, I want to just follow up on your thought
25 about if you prevent the infections. We have

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1 considerable evidence. It is association evidence but
2 there's considerable evidence that there is a necessity
3 here. HPV infection is a necessity in the overall causal
4 process that leads to cervical cancer.

5 What I've been struggling with all along is
6 this issue of sufficiency. You had used as an example,
7 and it's probably a very reasonable approximation, maybe
8 for every 100 infections that you would prevent, you would
9 prevent one case of cervical cancer.

10 If I knew that if I prevented those 100, I would
11 prevent the one case of cervical cancer, I would be
12 persuaded that I'm achieving something very important.

13 I'm not of the perspective that I have to know if I prevent
14 100 infections that I'm preventing 100 bad things.

15 My big concern is that I may prevent -- if,
16 in fact, I have 100 percent efficacy as a result, then
17 I can be confident that when I'm preventing all 100 of
18 the infections with my 100 percent efficacy that I am
19 preventing those 1 percent of the cases of cervical cancer
20 that will follow.

21 My concern is if I prevent 80 of the 100, I
22 may well be missing the one, in fact, that would have
23 resulted in cervical cancer. If I have 80 percent
24 efficacy or 90 percent efficacy even, I may have almost
25 no efficacy against what I really care about.

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1 It's the sufficiency issue that I keep saying. It
2 seems to me that because this is a setting where the
3 numbers suggest that it's something on the order of 50
4 or 100 people who will have HPV infection for everyone
5 one that eventually will over their lifetime have cervical
6 cancer, this is clearly a situation where it's far more
7 complex than simply saying is the vaccine going to prevent
8 the initial infection.

9 What I'm struggling with here is what is it
10 that we have to achieve in order to be confident that
11 we are actually having a meaningful impact on what we
12 really care about which is reducing the rate of occurrence
13 of clinical events.

14 Now, we focused on those clinical events being
15 primarily cervical cancer. I would, however, accept a
16 broader sense of clinical events, i.e., if we believe
17 that we are also achieving a reducing in the need for
18 invasive surgical interventions, etc., that's part of
19 the overall benefit as well, although I think our highest
20 priority clinical event here is
21 preventing cervical cancer

22 So the bottom line is we acknowledge we're
23 preventing many more cases of infection than we are
24 clinical sequelae, important clinical sequelae. I just
25 want to know that when we do get this reduction it

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1 translates into a meaningful reduction in cervical
2 cancer.

3 DR. SNIDER: Could I just quickly respond and
4 say, Tom, I think you and I are in agreement. All I'm
5 saying is that if we don't look at persistent infection
6 as one of the endpoints, it seems to me that would be
7 a shame because we're not preventing persistent
8 infection. I'm not optimistic that CIN 2 and 3 are going
9 to be prevented.

10 DR. FLEMING: So you're saying that's in your
11 vision of what the markers would have to be. That's one
12 of the necessary components that has to be impacted.

13 DR. SNIDER: Right.

14 DR. FLEMING: I'm very willing to accept that.
15 I'm struggling with what are the other elements that
16 give me a sufficiency condition here such that when I
17 see persistent infection and what else, is this going
18 to be adequate to be reasonably confident I'm having an
19 impact on cervical cancer rates.

20 DR. DAUM: Okay. We're going to stay on this
21 issue before we go on so people who want to talk to this
22 very issue. Dr. Reeves, Dr. Felix, Dr. Kohl.

23 DR. REEVES: Just a quickie of something that
24 I would have liked to have heard and I don't see any of
25 the NCI people that can give the answer. I think this

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1 vaccine to prevent cervical cancer is going to be unique
2 among vaccines. Diphtheria, influenza, and many of the
3 vaccines I'm aware of work very quickly.

4 Rolando Herrera, I believe, two years ago
5 presented some very elegant modeling studies of the effect
6 of vaccination on the rates of cervical cancer world wide
7 which, again, is the end disease we're trying to deal
8 with.

9 In essence he showed that it was going to be
10 approximately two decades before any effect was seen.
11 I think this rather important information, something to
12 take into consideration both in looking at whether we're
13 going to approve or recommend approval for accelerated
14 licensure. But two to three decades is a long time to
15 actually see an effect from something. I
16 suspect that the actual effect on surgical procedures
17 for high-grade dysplasia or CIN 3 with the actual public
18 health effect and efficacy of this is probably going to
19 be in terms of decades as well. I think some kind of
20 presentation of that kind of information would have been
21 very helpful.

22 DR. DAUM: Dr. Felix and Dr. Kohl, this very
23 issue we're on.

24 DR. FELIX: I appreciate the concerns that
25 Fleming has. I have the identical concerns. However,

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1 if you're proposing that by producing 80 percent or 90
2 percent of the HPV you may not be reducing the 10 percent
3 that will proceed to cancer. The same identical argument
4 can be used for the more distal surrogate endpoint which
5 would be high-grade dysplasia or CIN 2, CIN 3.

6 If you prevent 90 percent of CIN 2, CIN 3 it
7 is perhaps that 10 percent that you don't progress that
8 you don't protect for that will progress to cervical
9 cancer. I don't think it is reasonable to expect a trial
10 with an endpoint of cervical cancer. I don't think it
11 will happen if that's the case.

12 I think Dixie was correct. I think we need
13 to keep assurances that all of the reasonable endpoints
14 will be looked at, that we're going to look at persistent
15 virology, and the issue that I'm most concerned with that
16 I hope we are going to address very soon, the issue of
17 what interval does persistence truly become meaningful.
18

19 Then have relative assurance that we are going
20 to see CIN 2, CIN 3 data. It is, I think, within the
21 realm of this committee to insist that the trial for the
22 latter be finished by the time the accelerated approval
23 for the virological endpoints come out so that we could
24 guarantee that the second trial or the second observation
25 would happen.

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1 I don't think that it is reasonable to expect
2 anymore than the surrogates that are still going to leave
3 doubt as to the efficacy of the vaccine.

4 DR. DAUM: I think in our own way we are
5 starting to build consensus.

6 Dr. Kohl next. This very issue. We're still
7 there. Then Dr. Unger, Katz, and Sheets.

8 DR. KOHL: I'm feeling a consensus also
9 hopefully, what I'm thinking is the consensus as the same
10 thing other people are thinking.

11 DR. DAUM: We'll find out.

12 DR. KOHL: Being at this end of the table, all
13 the way at the end, this is the Dixie memorial seat down
14 here, I'm trying to think as a virologist now. We are
15 dealing with a virus but a virus that has an interesting
16 effect, namely cancer.

17 I'm trying to think what we know about -- at
18 least what we've been presented about the immunology or
19 the protection against first infection. Perhaps more
20 importantly the immunology against cancer, the prevention
21 of cancer.

22 I don't think we've heard much to anything about
23 the immunology or the prevention of cancer. Most of
24 what's in the literature, that I'm familiar with at least,
25 regarding the viral like particles is the elicitation

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1 of neutralizing antibody.

2 Yet, we know that the -- or we think we know
3 that what causes cancer are the E6/E7 transforming
4 elements. Then there's the whole issue of latency.

5 What I want to get around to in a sort of sequitious
6 way is following some of what Dr. Fleming is talking about.

7 What if we have that heterogenetic population where a
8 small percentage, because of immunological aspect we
9 don't understand, is very susceptible.

10 And what if paradoxically neutralizing
11 antibody doesn't have a positive effect but has a negative
12 effect? It's wild. It's outside the box, but it's one
13 of those things we just don't know about. I think all
14 these uncertainties would push me towards a more rigorous
15 endpoint as we think about surrogate endpoints.

16 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

17 Dr. Unger.

18 DR. UNGER: I just want to remind everybody
19 about the difficulty in the assays in talking about
20 infection and persistent infection.

21 DR. DAUM: Talk right into the microphone.

22 DR. UNGER: Okay.

23 DR. DAUM: Thanks. Sorry.

24 DR. UNGER: I'll start again. I just want to
25 remind everybody about the difficulty of establishing

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1 infection, the difficulty both in the assays and the
2 sample. I think that we need to be sure that the sample
3 is taken appropriately and the appropriate amount of the
4 sample is put into the assay.

5 You can have the most eloquent and sensitive
6 assay in the world but if the sample is not the appropriate
7 sample and enough is not put in, it's going to make your
8 definition of endpoint and infection a moot.

9 I think that the literature is very clear that
10 the assays and the sampling will muddy the kind of pictures
11 that you see. We need to be clear on what kind of
12 documentation we want to see or should be part of looking
13 at this kind of persistent infection.

14 I think that the better the assays have become
15 and the more standardized the sampling has become, the
16 clearer the picture is as to what the situation -- not
17 that it's clear now but there is starting to be some
18 consensus.

19 I think part of the confusion is the definition
20 of persistent infection and the timing that should be
21 required in order to say what persistent is versus a normal
22 endpoint of clearing of an infection that would go away
23 on its own.

24 DR. DAUM: Dr. Katz at last.

25 DR. KATZ: I would like to go back again to

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1 what Dixie has said and what Karen has said. Viruses
2 are all different and it's very inappropriate to make
3 generalizations because this virus does this, that virus
4 does that.

5 But the example that's been used is a reasonable
6 one of hepatitis B. Why did they start looking for
7 hepatitis B vaccines? Not just to prevent acute disease
8 but because Palmer Beasley showed in Taiwan where they
9 had a high incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma and that
10 hepatitis B infection led to hepatocellular carcinoma.

11
12 The studies that have gone on there over the
13 years now have shown they markedly reduced hepatocellular
14 carcinoma to a rare disease in Taiwan because they gave
15 vaccine to young people.

16 Now, it does prevent hepatitis over disease
17 but it doesn't prevent occult infection and you may have
18 occult abbreviated infection. This, as I mentioned in
19 response to Karen, is shown by the fact that the vaccine
20 only gives you antibodies to one antigen, the surface
21 antigen.

22 You can show that vaccinated people, though
23 they don't have the disease, develop antibodies to the
24 core antigen which indicates they have not only been
25 infected but they have been infected sufficiently to

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1 arouse an immune response.

2 Those people who have totally lost detectable
3 antibody to the surface antigen nevertheless resist
4 developing clinical disease or chemical disease. We have
5 a model which is not a perfect paradigm, but I think we
6 do have a model, at least, of where preventing an infection
7 from developing beyond an abortive state does prevent
8 the development of cancer.

9 I think the long-term effects of this can be
10 in some ways analogous, if you will. Not a perfect one
11 but I'm encouraged that if you can prevent infection with
12 these oncogenic papilloma viruses you may well prevent
13 cancer.

14 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Katz.

15 Dr. Sheets.

16 DR. SHEETS: I guess I'm simply a gynecologic
17 oncologist. Not a virologist nor immunologist, nor a
18 vaccinologist. When I think of human papilloma virus
19 infection, I think of the transvaginal infection that
20 may or may not ever be systemically manifested. Even
21 invasive cancer you may or may not show systemic
22 antibodies to E6/E7 my understanding is.

23 When we think about this vaccine and we think
24 about this vaccine and we think about proximate surrogates
25 or distal surrogates as to what that might eventually

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1 prevent invasive cancer, we have to think about what's
2 happening with the mucosal barrier.

3 The vaccine is supposed to prevent infection
4 by neutralizing antibodies being present in cervical
5 mucosal discharge that keeps the virus from infecting
6 the epithelium. That's my understanding of what the
7 vaccine is supposed to do.

8 We don't know, and I think hepatitis is
9 certainly a good surrogate systemic infection to look
10 at for the development of a cancer. But what we don't
11 know is the latency issues of HPV. We don't know that.

12
13 You are discussing the fact that latent virus
14 associated with hepatitis B may cause -- does cause
15 hepatocellular cancer. Eradicating that virus you may
16 get infected but having the antibody potential
17 systemically to kill that viral infection does preventing
18 the latent state leading to hepatocellular cancer is a
19 surrogate marker for HPV infection.

20 I simply don't know that. I don't know if
21 that's true, but I think it's out of the venue of this
22 discussion to decide whether we're going to move forward
23 with a fast track for this vaccine or not.

24 I think what it underscores is the fact that
25 we don't know how HPV induces ultimately cervical cancer

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1 in the epithelium and what the immune response plays in
2 that role for therapeutic interventions or prophylactic
3 interventions.

4 But we have to assume that the stuff the vaccine
5 is causing is simply to block the infection itself and
6 may have secondary effects of T cell responses, etc.,
7 etc., should there be a small amount of virus that
8 penetrates the epithelium and causes a T cell response
9 and we do get efficacy in that system. We don't know
10 that yet.

11 Maybe the NCI knows that but I don't at this
12 point in time. I think we have to look at the data that's
13 here and the decision that we have to make is one step
14 away from cervical cancer. The question is how many steps
15 away will we allow. If we allow it to be too far away,
16 will we ever know the real answer. My
17 concern ultimately, and it's a step beyond what we're
18 talking about now, is the apparent efficacy of the vaccine
19 is so great for preventing infection will we ever be able
20 to carry a placebo group forward.

21 DR. DAUM: Can you help me with one more
22 expansion of your comments?

23 DR. SHEETS: Maybe.

24 DR. DAUM: Are you suggesting that there is
25 a scenario -- supposing we had a crystal ball here and

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1 we knew that this vaccine was being universally used now
2 and it meant that HPV infection was efficacy 100 percent
3 prevented. Can you imagine a scenario with that being
4 true where it would not have an impact on cervical cancer?

5 DR. SHEETS: 100 percent efficacy for both male
6 and female?

7 DR. DAUM: Yeah.

8 DR. SHEETS: So that you're not re-exposing
9 them chronically to the virus?

10 DR. DAUM: Yes. Let's go whole hog.

11 DR. SHEETS: How could it not? If you
12 eradicate HPV it would impact. No doubt.

13 DR. DAUM: Okay. Good.

14 DR. REEVES: It would be next on the list behind
15 measles.

16 DR. FLEMING: Let me just make sure your
17 question is clarified. When you say 100 percent that
18 suggest to me that you mean 100 percent across all types
19 and 100 percent across all time. Then if that is the
20 case, then I'm happy to say yes, too. There's a lot to
21 that question.

22 DR. DAUM: Let me clarify. Let me say all
23 time, yes, but all types, no, only the types in the
24 vaccine. Yes, 100 percent against all the types.

25 I'm trying to get a sense from people who really

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1 understand the subject which does not include me, whether
2 or not it is conceivably possible to prevent HPV infection
3 completely and at the same time not assume that cancer
4 is prevented also. That's what I'm trying to understand.

5 Is there such a scenario?

6 Does anyone want to speak to this? Diane.

7 DR. GRIFFIN: No. If you're talking about HPV
8 16 induced cancer, if you prevent all infections, you
9 will prevent HPV 16 induced cancer. I also want
10 -- I mean, I think the links are extraordinarily strong
11 and we certainly understand a whole lot more about how
12 HPV induces cancer than about how hepatitis induces cancer
13 which, as far as I understand, we have relatively little
14 understanding of that pathway.

15 We understand that much better for the HPV.
16 We don't have a perfect understanding of that but it does
17 require infection and it does require infection that is
18 over some period of time and I don't know what that period
19 of time is.

20 I think you are ignoring a lot of virologic
21 data that has come in for a long period of time about
22 these links and about the pathogenesis of this process.

23 DR. DAUM: I'm going to try and maintain some
24 sense of order here. I wrote the rules myself and jumped
25 in, but I have Dr. O'Connor first, then Dr. Felix, Ms.

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1 Fisher, Drs. Reeves, Katz, Kohl.

2 DR. O'CONNOR: I get the impression there are
3 a lot of topics floating around here. I wanted to go
4 back and address endpoints for just a minute and say very
5 quickly that I agree with both Dixie and Juan as far as
6 the endpoints go.

7 I think there is enough evidence to indicate
8 that persistent papilloma virus infection is associated
9 with CIN to the point that it can be considered a vaccine
10 failure, surrogate or not. Certainly identification of
11 it is accelerated enough that it might be considered
12 surrogate.

13 I think there is excellent evidence to indicate
14 that CIN 3 is associated with cervical cancer, although
15 the information regarding CIN 2 is not as clear because
16 criteria for diagnosis are not that reproducible. I
17 think there's enough there to say that CIN 2 should be
18 lumped in with CIN 3. CIN 1 doesn't work just because
19 it's a polyglot and the diagnosis is extremely
20 irreproducible.

21 The last thing I want to say is that we're
22 talking really about histologic diagnoses and not
23 cytologic diagnoses. You need to be clear on that. Even
24 though the specificity of cytology gets better as the
25 abnormality gets worse, you still have a significant

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1 number of HSILs, and I'm talking about cytology, that
2 will have no dysplasia or low-grade dysplasia on biopsy.

3
4 I think it's best to leave that as a screen
5 test. When you're talking about endpoints talk about
6 a directed biopsy or excision procedure that will give
7 you a histologic diagnosis.

8 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. O'Connor.

9 Dr. Felix.

10 DR. FELIX: I am going to have to politely
11 reverse Dr. Sheets' disagreement with me and disagree
12 with her. I don't think that necessarily the function
13 of the vaccine is to prevent infection. I think that
14 you can have an extremely efficacious HPV vaccine if you
15 abort infection early.

16 In other words, induce regression at an
17 accelerated rate. We know that regression results in
18 prevention of cervical cancer. I don't think that you
19 necessarily have to prevent infection in order to make
20 an effective vaccine. Obviously the examples have been
21 brought forth for hepatitis B.

22 I think that it's a very reasonable analogy
23 to make at this point. I think if you have cellular
24 immunity that will act in aborting a lesion early on,
25 you can, in fact, enhance prevention of cervical cancer.

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1 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

2 I have Ms. Fisher, then Drs. Reeves, Katz, Kohl,
3 Palese, and Kim.

4 MS. FISHER: In terms of the idea of
5 eradicating HPV infection by vaccinating all women and
6 men, how do you know you're not going to put pressure
7 on an organism to change into a vaccine resistant form
8 when you're only using certain types such as HPV 16 and
9 18?

10 DR. DAUM: That's a provocative question. I
11 don't think we do know.

12 DR. GRIFFIN: You won't change those into new
13 types but you may have the opportunity for other types
14 to now fill those niches and we're not going to know that
15 until we do the studies. That's the reason one of the
16 things that needs to be incorporated into the studies
17 is looking at these other types.

18 DR. DAUM: People would have to be mind of those
19 things, I would think.

20 Dr. Reeves.

21 DR. REEVES: I had a couple of points and they
22 kind of go back a bit. I disagree completely that if
23 we eradicated HPV from the face of the earth, all types
24 of infected genital mucosal, that we would necessarily
25 prevent cervical cancer.

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1 If, for example, we eradicated hepatitis B with
2 a vaccine program and we eradicated hepatitis C, we would
3 not, in fact, eradicate hepatocellular carcinoma or
4 cirrhosis.

5 DR. DAUM: Due to those agents?

6 DR. REEVES: I'm talking about the disease
7 because the disease is a complex multi-factorial disease
8 of which HPV is currently the most important associated
9 risk factor.

10 Unfortunately, I remember in the old days, and
11 I think some probably remembers this, too, when herpes
12 II caused this disease. It is not necessarily a simple
13 disease. We have an ideologic agent highly associated
14 with the disease and vaccine will probably have a major
15 effect on it.

16 I go back to hepatitis B. The timing of the
17 vaccine, as I recall, was very important in the prevention
18 of hepatocellular carcinoma. It was infections of young
19 children I think more associated around the time of
20 delivery or transplacental transmission that was
21 important. The timing in which this vaccine is given
22 is very important. We talk about naive women, women who
23 have not been infected with the agent before, that's
24 probably not the group that's going to be vaccinated.
25 I don't think we always know what naive means in terms

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1 of this agent.

2 Finally, there is at least one agent that I
3 am aware of, unless it has changed, respiratory censishal
4 virus, an apparently very good vaccine made worse. That
5 possibility --

6 DR. KATZ: It wasn't a good vaccine. That's
7 not fair.

8 DR. DAUM: Can you clarify one thing that you
9 said? If you prevented, let's say, two serotypes of HPV,
10 would you prevent an infection by those two viruses?
11 Would you prevent cancer caused by those two viruses?

12 DR. REEVES: I think what we want to do is
13 prevent the affects of the infection, so preventing the
14 affects or ameliorating the affects of the infection.
15 Preventing the infection would obviously do that but one
16 would not have to prevent the infection to ameliorate
17 the affects of that infection if that involves
18 integration, over expression of E6/E7, etc. I think
19 obviously preventing the infection would prevent the
20 disease that resulted from that infection, yes.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you. Thanks very helpful.

22 Dr. Kohl, Dr. Palese, Dr. Kim.

23 DR. KOHL: I want to genteelly object to one
24 of my chairman's constructs.

25 DR. DAUM: For the first time.

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1 DR. KOHL: Absolutely. He proposed the
2 possibility of 100 percent prevention of an infection
3 and then the resultant 100 percent prevention of a disease
4 associated with that infection, namely, prevention, let's
5 say, HPV 16 and then prevention of HPV 16 associated
6 cancer. I would agree that is probable.

7 But I think as one of my favorite people, Ross
8 Perot, said, "The devil is in the details." He's not
9 really one of my favorite people. I can't think of any
10 vaccine -- any vaccine, let alone a mucosal vaccine, that
11 is capable of preventing 100 percent of infection. I
12 can't think of that as a possible scenario.

13 Therefore, I'm left with some finite percentage
14 of people in whom the prevention won't be complete, who
15 will still get infected. It's that small percentage,
16 because they have some unknown immunological situation
17 that Barbara Fisher alluded to yesterday, that causes
18 some people to progress who I'm most concerned about.

19 Do they have latent infection of some kind?
20 Does antibody make that worse? I don't know. It's that
21 little group of people, 5 percent, 10 percent, 15 percent,
22 that I'm concerned about and that's a big unknown with
23 this vaccine.

24 DR. DAUM: Steve, my comments were by way of
25 requesting information from experts to try and get at

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1 the solidness of the link between infection and the
2 consequences. Of course, it can't be 100 percent
3 effective but in hemophilus there are some people who
4 are clearly still at risk of disease because we still
5 have a few cases occurring despite full immunization.

6 DR. KOHL: In some of them we know why.

7 DR. DAUM: The 100 percent was a hypothetical
8 discussion.

9 DR. KOHL: But it muddies the water, I think,
10 because it leaves out that 5 or 10 percent who will still
11 be infected for sure and whom we know very little about
12 why that's the case and what a vaccine will particularly
13 do in that setting in those people.

14 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

15 Dr. Palese.

16 DR. PALESE: I just want to raise the question
17 about the safety of the preparations which are being
18 discussed right now. These are, if I understand it right,
19 inactivated so they are viral like particles.

20 I want to ask whether there is any evidence
21 that they have any unacceptable side effects, or that
22 there were any exacerbations of any kind of disease
23 associated with giving this experimental preparation.

24 Is anything known and what is the longest time
25 period that we can consider here so we can have the

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1 earliest preparations being administered? Is there
2 anything known? Have we heard anything?

3 DR. DAUM: I'm going to call on Dr. Goldenthal
4 because my sense is that although safety is crucial to
5 any plan to go forward with the deployment of this vaccine,
6 it hasn't been among the things that we've been asked
7 to consider today, at least head on. How would you like
8 us to take up this question of safety, Dr. Goldenthal?

9 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, I think that it's a
10 reasonable topic for discussion, especially when we get
11 to question No. 2 because one of the issues there would
12 be potentially the amount of safety data that we would
13 have prior to licensure. I think it's a legitimate thing.

14 In answer to your question, I think I can say
15 in general there's been maybe three years or so of
16 follow-up on individuals who have received VLPs in various
17 trials. The numbers are fairly limited at this point.
18 Maybe a few thousand at most.

19 It would be hard based to make, you know, based
20 on -- while there's nothing that's been troubling that
21 I'm aware of, it also would be hard to make a lot of
22 conclusions at this point.

23 DR. DAUM: I think when we focus more on this
24 accelerated approval question and I think we need to
25 return to this issue, at least only to state what we

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1 believe would need to be done before we would be
2 comfortable.

3 Dr. Kim.

4 DR. KIM: Well, we heard a lot about some
5 aspects of HPV infection and how infection would either
6 regress or persist. Again, we also talk a lot on the
7 issues of a persistent infection which has been very
8 arbitrarily defined and interpreted amongst all of us.

9 I have not got the concept yet. What is the
10 biological relevance of persistent infection,
11 particularly as it relates to CIN 2 and 3, not cervical
12 cancer at this juncture?

13 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

14 Dr. Goldberg.

15 DR. GOLDBERG: My question -- it's a comment
16 really. We saw a lot of data on different intervals for
17 defining persistence, the time between the two successive
18 observations.

19 It seems to me that a study such as the one
20 we heard from the NCI yesterday should allow us to be
21 able to look at the distribution of lengths of persistence
22 in a large population and then relate back to later events.

23
24 I would like to see that kind of thinking
25 incorporated into the trials that are designed regardless

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1 of what endpoints we choose because I think this will
2 be relevant as we go forward.

3 DR. DAUM: Dr. Sheets is scheduled to speak
4 next and maybe I would ask before you make what comment
5 you wish, could you address Dr. Goldberg's question in
6 that if persistence is going to be used as an endpoint,
7 vis-a-vis question 1b, then what definition does a real
8 expert in this recommend that we use? Clarify your
9 question first.

10 DR. GOLDBERG: Okay. I'm not convinced that
11 I saw anything that would give me great comfort in any
12 of the definitions. What I'm suggesting is that as we
13 design trials going forward that we incorporate the
14 ability to look at the distributions of the lengths of
15 time between the successive positive tests for HPV.

16 I think particularly the information from the
17 control groups will inform out thinking with regard to
18 the influence of this on the later endpoints such as CIN
19 2 and 3. What I'm thinking is that if you cut that
20 interval too short, you're taking away all the cases.

21 You're using cases that would have resolved
22 by themselves that will have no impact. If the interval
23 is too long, you may be practically there. I think you
24 can get some information.

25 I think the NCI trial that we heard yesterday,

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1 if I understand the data correctly, and if the remainder
2 of the cohort other than the ones that were positive at
3 entry are examined over time and you may get some important
4 information.

5 It's sort of like developing a receiver
6 operating characteristic curve on different cut points
7 for the definition of what the interval between successive
8 positive HPV tests are that would be meaningful later.

9 DR. DAUM: Now, Dr. Sheets. Thank you.

10 DR. SHEETS: I don't think I can speak
11 specifically to the NCI close session data talked about
12 yesterday.

13 DR. DAUM: Nor do we really want you to.

14 DR. SHEETS: But I do think it's relevant to
15 say at this point in time in 2001 that we don't know the
16 answer to your question in regards to what represents
17 a persistent infection that's clinically relevant, or
18 if that is even important depending on your time point
19 or endpoint or what you want to prevent.

20 Ultimately we want to prevent invasive cervical
21 cancer, both adeno and squamose. That's the goal here.

22 We don't know whether we can translate HPV presence,
23 high-risk oncogenic presence, specific to the viral type
24 being vaccinated against as being a surrogate for that
25 or not. That's the discussion I think is on the table.

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1
2 I'm not an expert in that in terms of virology
3 persistence, but I would say that I don't know yet from
4 the data that I've seen in the world's literature, nor
5 heard in closed session that I can make that statement.

6 It should be incorporated into whatever trial we decide
7 is endpoints.

8 I guess within the bounds of what can be
9 presented here in open session compared to closed, I would
10 like to hear from Doug Lowy his point of view in terms
11 of what this vaccine or vaccines in general that are
12 prophylactic would probably be the best way to phrase
13 this. A prophylactic vaccine using VLPs theoretically
14 should be doing for us in terms of how it interrupts the
15 HPV cycle or if we know that at all in this point in time
16 because I think it's an important consideration in
17 answering Dr. Felix's disagreement with me, disagreeing
18 with me over what we're agreeing as to whether you actually
19 do get an infection, yet dissipate that infection so it
20 doesn't become clinically relevant and the vaccine does
21 do that for us.

22 My concern is that we're using a systemic system
23 both across the table and over here, an hepatocellular
24 infection that is not necessarily the same as what we're
25 talking about here today in the mucosal immune system.

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1 I'm just interested in hearing what Dr. Lowy could point
2 out in that. Is that possible?

3 DR. DAUM: Is Dr. Lowy here?

4 PARTICIPANT: Yeah. Right there.

5 DR. DAUM: Do you care to comment on this?
6 You're not obliged to.

7 DR. LOWY: Ellen, thank you very much. I think
8 that the issues that are being raised are very pertinent
9 and relevant to the discussion. My colleague, John
10 Schiller, may want to amplify on some of my comments.

11 My sense of the VLP vaccine is that it is going
12 to be doing -- it is basically going to reduce the
13 inoculum. We haven't talked much about viral inoculum
14 but with most infectious diseases the size of the inoculum
15 has a very important impact on disease downstream.

16 By reducing the inoculum there should be one
17 of two outcomes. One is that you would completely prevent
18 infection, and the other would be that you would reduce
19 the number of infectious hits.

20 There also is a possibility it's ambiguous
21 whether the target, which is the transition zone of the
22 cervix, is the immediate site of infection or whether
23 there might be a remote site distant from that.

24 You could imagine that antibodies might have
25 a further impact on reduction of going to the site of

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1 the target, if you will, analogous to the hepatitis
2 situation where you get infection but it doesn't get in
3 sufficient numbers to the target. I think it's ambiguous
4 which way that would work. In the best case scenario
5 it would be a complete prevention of infection but I
6 certainly wouldn't expect it to do that in all
7 individuals.

8 In terms of the long-term persistence of
9 antibodies, I suppose it's hypothetically possible that
10 might have an adverse impact, but there is no theoretical
11 reason to believe that you are going to be -- that it
12 would have such an impact.

13 We haven't seen in the limited trials that we
14 have done which involves maybe 100 individuals, we haven't
15 seen a group of people who are particularly resistant
16 to responding in terms of immunity or particularly
17 susceptible when we look at the bell-shaped curve.

18 The concern of Dr. Kohl that maybe you're
19 picking out a particular group of people, I think while
20 it's hypothetically possible, I don't think we have a
21 coherent notion that the latent infection would be more
22 likely to be more serious because of antibodies being
23 present, although I think hypothetically that might be
24 a possibility.

25 With regard to persistent infection, I think

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1 that Dr. Fleming is, of course, raising a very important
2 issue about the duration of infection.

3 It's one of the reasons why when one picks
4 persistent you would like to have a relatively long period
5 of time, thereby increasing the probability that by
6 reducing those persistent infections that you really
7 would be having an impact on the clinically important
8 downstream events.

9 The precise number whether it should be six
10 months, 12 months, 24 months is going to be somewhat
11 arbitrary which is what Mark was trying to point out
12 yesterday. There are some data now, and there will be
13 better data.

14 Even when you get the better data it's going
15 to be a balancing act. I guess with Dr. Wilkinson, I
16 think that he raises a very important issue of the question
17 of referring people for colposcopy.

18 My question for Dr. Wilkinson would be if you
19 get referred to for colposcopy, what's the likelihood
20 that you would be biopsied? Because if you were going
21 to be biopsied, then you presumably would be out of a
22 clinical trial.

23 DR. DAUM: Having said all that and being
24 practically oriented, given all your expertise and given
25 the arbitrary nature of the decision that I'm about to

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1 ask you for, if you were to pick, and emphasis on the
2 word "if," persistent infection as an endpoint, what
3 definition would you use for that?

4 DR. LOWY: I really am relying on Mark because
5 he is our expert. He is our medical epidemiologist.
6 He feels that an appropriate balance would be a year,
7 that you will be clearing out most of the, if you will,
8 clinically irrelevant infections and it will have a high
9 predictive value of preventing significant proportion
10 of the downstream events.

11 DR. DAUM: One year. Thank you very much.

12 Okay. The next people to speak are Drs. Snider and
13 Myers. Are these clarifications of this very issue?
14

15 DR. SNIDER: Yes.

16 DR. DAUM: Okay. Then Drs. Griffin and
17 Snider. Dr. Snider, you're next anyway. Why don't you
18 go first and then Dr. Griffin on this very issue. Then
19 we'll go on to Dr. Myers next.

20 DR. SNIDER: I would like to just pick up on
21 the comments that were just made. The trade off, as I
22 understand it, is even more profound in the sense that
23 it's not just specificity of the study endpoints, but
24 there are some clinical implications, some ethical
25 implications in terms of the intervals you choose.

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1 If you choose a shorter interval, of course,
2 then you have the possibility that's already been
3 mentioned or the certainty that's already been mentioned,
4 that you'll be calling a lot of endpoints, significant
5 endpoints which are not significant in the sense that
6 they will regress.

7 There also is a clinical corla in the sense
8 that it sounds as if whatever interval is chosen, there
9 will be some interventions that again will have some not
10 only economic cost but some morbidity and at least
11 psychological morbidity and physical morbidity
12 associated with them.

13 The longer you go the more specificity you get,
14 but then if I understood correctly, for two reasons you
15 may wind up with more cancers. One is because there are
16 a few women who would rapidly progress. If you went to
17 two years, for example, there are a few women that I think
18 he said you would lose. I think he said you would lose
19 but I think what he meant was they would progress quite
20 rapidly to cancer.

21 The other, of course, is this whole issue of
22 compliance in clinical trials. The longer you wait, the
23 more you signal that this is not all that important and
24 women start dropping out and they don't come in for that
25 two-year visit.

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1 Again, you run the risk of having these very
2 serious outcomes that have more morbidity and perhaps
3 even mortality associated with it. It is a delegate
4 balancing act.

5 I just wanted to at least indicate some of my
6 understanding about some of the value judgements and some
7 of the ethical and other implications of making that
8 choice. There is no exactly right answer right now.

9 The other thing that has to do with persistent
10 infection in terms of how you define it is not just the
11 interval but it has to do with how many specimens you
12 want. Also, as has been pointed out, how you obtain those
13 specimens and what assay you use. These are all
14 critical issues in terms of defining persistence to have
15 to be looked at very carefully. I'm not sure this
16 committee can get into all of those details but there
17 are some general principles, I think, we could probably
18 articulate about what we would like to see with regard
19 to the intensity in which one investigates and the
20 characteristics of the test.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dixie.

22 I have Drs. Griffin, Myers, Freeman, Pagliusi,
23 and Kohl.

24 DR. GRIFFIN: I just wanted to comment on and
25 get Doug to expand on the reason that persistent infection

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1 is such an important part of the pathogenic process that
2 we are trying to prevent and also examine in these women.

3 It's my understanding that the longer the virus
4 continues to replicate in its site, the increased
5 likelihood that you'll get integration, which is a random
6 event, and other oncogenic changes in those cells that
7 will then eventually result in carcinoma.

8 That is sort of the biologic principles under
9 which one becomes interested in persistent infection and
10 the length of persistent infection. But I would like
11 Doug's comment on that.

12 DR. LOWY: This is a series of genetic changes
13 presumably and the more opportunity you have in terms
14 of chronologically, the more likely it is to happen.

15 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

16 Dr. Myers, please.

17 DR. MYERS: I'm not a papilloma virologist but
18 I think we need to be careful about some of the terms
19 we're using like inoculum and persistence and latency
20 and replication because we really don't know how to
21 measure those in the circumstances that we're talking
22 about.

23 I guess the question is, to go back to the
24 comment that you made, the reducing inoculum. Is that
25 really the intent or is what we're trying to do is alter

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1 the natural history of persistent outcome? I think
2 that's important if you go back to Dr. Reeves' comment
3 earlier.

4 This vaccine is not going to just be given to
5 naive individuals. I think we need to explore -- and
6 we haven't really talked much about this but we really
7 need to explore the intent to immunize the outcome from
8 the intent to immunize.

9 When we're talking about persistence and when
10 we're talking about high-grade disease, we need to address
11 that in individuals that are both HPV 16 and 18 positive
12 as well as naive because we really don't understand these
13 virologic events in the natural history of the clinical
14 setting. I think we've been skirting that issue.

15 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Myers.

16 Dr. Freeman.

17 DR. FREEMAN: I just wanted to make a brief
18 comment that the choice of these endpoints and, in
19 particular, the precision with which these endpoints can
20 be determined, I think, are incorporated into a trial
21 that would lead to an accelerated approval or further
22 I think are very important.

23 Not just from the point of view of demonstrating
24 that the vaccine works but in convincing the subjects
25 who will eventually receive -- the males and females who

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1 will eventually receive this vaccine if this thing
2 actually works.

3 I'm reminded of the comments of one of the
4 advocacy groups from yesterday that if the vaccine is
5 approved, it really has to be meaningful in order to get
6 compliance and usage to do what it's supposed to do.

7 The other thing is the physicians who are going
8 to administer the vaccine and monitor these patients
9 safely have to have a good idea about the -- have to be
10 convinced that the trial really demonstrated the efficacy
11 of the vaccine in terms of the way they understand the
12 disease process.

13 I'm not sure from all that I've heard, although
14 I am convinced of the association that has been mentioned,
15 the association between the HPV viruses and this disease.

16 I'm not sure how easy it's going to be to rely on the
17 HPV endpoints as indications for usage of the vaccine
18 practically.

19 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

20 Dr. Pagliusi.

21 DR. PAGLIUSI: Thank you. I would like to come
22 back to the persistence of infection to the balancing
23 act. I would like to address a question to the experts.

24 Maybe Doug Lowy could help me here.

25 If we would think of measuring persistent

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1 infection twice, three times, four times, what that
2 increase the confidence and the effectiveness of the
3 vaccine or the efficacy of the vaccine?

4 DR. DAUM: I'm not sure I understood the
5 question. May I ask you to clarify?

6 DR. PAGLIUSI: My question is addressing
7 persistence of infection. Dr. Lowy proposed that one
8 year may give us more confidence on the results. My
9 question is now if within this one year we would see three
10 positives or four positives.

11 DR. DAUM: Or two.

12 DR. PAGLIUSI: Or two, what are the balancing
13 here?

14 DR. LOWY: Sonia, I think that certainly it
15 would be preferable under ideal circumstances to sample
16 more frequently and to have recurrent positive results.

17 My impression is that if you had two positives separated
18 by whatever interval it was, you could then go back and
19 be quite sure that this was with the same variant or not
20 with the same variant. Then you could be quite
21 sure that the individual was continually infected with
22 the same virus or a different one. I think that would
23 be adequate.

24 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

25 Dr. Kohl.

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1 DR. KOHL: I was a little confused. Oh,
2 Dixie's not here. I think Dixie was implying that
3 different time periods, i.e., a 12-month persistence or
4 24-month persistence would some how affect and I think
5 he used the words "lose some women."

6 I was not under the impression that the amount
7 of time that was chosen for persistence would per se affect
8 how woman are followed for cervical cancer screening and
9 that women would still be followed according to standard
10 of care no matter what the time period were for what was
11 decided as persistence. Is that correct? So no matter
12 what you pick as a definition you're not going to "lose
13 people."

14 DR. DAUM: I think we're getting to a point
15 where people are locking in their ideas about what would
16 be the endpoint they most favor. But before we really
17 start systematically debriefing everybody of those few
18 points, I would like to ask people to consider this.

19 Is it possible, Karen, and I hope this is within
20 the spirit of your first question. Is it possible to
21 consider multiple endpoints? For example, is there a
22 possibility of designing research, a clinical
23 investigation, a vaccine trial if you will, that looked
24 at different endpoints in sequence with each other and
25 had sort of separate analyses for these different

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1 endpoints and sequence? Is that a feasible way to think
2 about this, or do we need to focus on just one?

3 Karen, I would like you to respond to that first
4 and then maybe others.

5 DR. GOLDENTHAL: I believe you could design
6 a trial that way. That isn't the way we have ordinarily
7 proceeded for preventive vaccines, but I think it's
8 theoretically possible obviously with rigorous
9 prospective statistical analyses plans and designation
10 of endpoints.

11 DR. DAUM: Does anyone want to comment on that
12 thought or that idea?

13 Dr. Kim.

14 DR. KIM: I was given the information that
15 somehow linkage has been not clearly delineated and some
16 question. I support the concept that perhaps two
17 endpoints can be incorporated. For example, the first
18 one would be persistent infection but second would be
19 truly translated into CIN 2 and 3 as secondary endpoint.

20 DR. DAUM: Okay. Thank you.

21 Dr. Decker. We haven't heard much from you
22 today.

23 DR. DECKER: Or yesterday.

24 DR. DAUM: Or yesterday. Here's your chance.

25 DR. DECKER: I'm glad you brought up a point

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1 you just did because I've been thinking about that. It
2 seems to me that if it ends up being decided that the
3 primary endpoint for a trial would be nonvirological.

4 Then I think it would be imperative that their
5 be co-primary or strong secondary endpoints that were
6 virological, if for no other reason than so that future
7 trials would be guided by the understanding of the links
8 between the virological and the clinical outcomes.

9 To me it almost goes without saying that it
10 would be essential that there be virological surveillance
11 and virological endpoints measured in any trial whose
12 primary endpoint was clinical.

13 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

14 Dr. Snider, Dr. Fleming next.

15 DR. SNIDER: I's just like briefly to address
16 that point, too, I think in view of the evolving
17 knowledge base, the rapidly evolving knowledge base
18 around this issue, having that kind of a trial may be
19 not only advantageous to the FDA, this committee, but
20 to the manufacturer as well because it allows you in one
21 trial to make adjustments as new information becomes
22 available rather than going out and having to redesign
23 the trial. There's a lower risk of having to redesign
24 trials.

25 DR. DAUM: Dr. Fleming is next.

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1 DR. FLEMING: Bob, I strongly endorse your
2 thought. I think in this setting where there is such
3 uncertainty, and I think Steve had mentioned it earlier,
4 it certainly leads me to be more cautious. The benefits
5 of looking at a multi-dimensional or multi-variate type
6 of outcome certainly does give us chance of capturing
7 a broader spectrum of the nature of what the effects are.

8 After we discuss this broad issue, in fact,
9 I had two or three other specific issues that I was hoping
10 to discuss that really relate to this, to two of the
11 domains of what I would think of as what might be the
12 dimensions of this surrogate.

13 DR. DAUM: Go ahead.

14 DR. FLEMING: Okay. Well, one of them is we've
15 -- my understanding is we're going to be focusing
16 predominately on vaccines that would target the HPV 16
17 and 18 types. Certainly as we look at outcome marker
18 surrogates, the ones that will be most sensitive to the
19 effects of these vaccines will also be type specific.

20 At least as I'm thinking through my own
21 formulation of what might be a surrogate or an accelerated
22 approval measure versus what might be a full approval
23 measure, it would be the distinction in accelerated
24 approval of allowing focus more on those type specific
25 outcomes but full approval on more validation of a global

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1 benefit.

2 My sense of how important that distinction is
3 I have uncertainties. My understanding from the data
4 that was presented yesterday is something on the order
5 of 60 to 70 percent of CIN2/3 as associated with HPV 16/18.

6
7 Before you comment on that, you can confirm
8 or refute that, but my more important question is what
9 is the nature of the -- how much of cervical cancer is
10 attributable to 16/18? Will there be an opportunistic
11 influence here? If you essentially reduce to eliminate
12 16 to 18, what influence does that have? Could we expect
13 that will have on the global rate of cervical cancer?

14 So there's two elements to this. The one
15 element is in the current milieu of the mixture of these
16 types, what fraction of cervical cancer is attributable
17 to 16/18 and if you eliminate that causal influence, are
18 there opportunistic influences that would alter what the
19 ultimate reduction in the rate of cervical cancer would
20 be?

21 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, across studies I would
22 say that about 60 percent of cervical cancers overall
23 globally are due to 16 and 18. That's a rough
24 approximation.

25 I would suspect that in the U.S., as I mentioned

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1 yesterday, the adenocarcinoma components is becoming of
2 increasing importance so that the 18 component, in my
3 mind, has a lot of importance here.

4 In terms of CIN 2/3 I think somewhere in the range of
5 50 to 70 percent of CIN 2/3 may be attributed to type
6 16 and 18.

7 DR. FLEMING: So you are confirming the
8 approximate CIN 2/3 numbers that I gave, around 60 to
9 70 percent. You're suggesting that under the current
10 milieu that there is a corresponding comparable
11 percentage of cervical cancer that can then be
12 attributable to 16/18.

13 The third aspect of it was is there any sense
14 if you eliminate that component, can we conclude that
15 we'll be left with then 40 percent, or could there be
16 an opportunistic aspect here such that the actual
17 reduction in the rate of cervical cancer may be less than
18 that?

19 DR. GOLDENTHAL: I think what you're asking
20 about in part is replacement. In other words, if you
21 eliminated some types would you have replacement with
22 others. I've actually looked in the literature for that
23 very -- to address that very question.

24 I didn't see evidence from the literature that
25 removing, let's say, type 16 would be more likely to cause

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1 persistence of other types. Again, none of this is in
2 the context of a vaccine trial so that has to be kept
3 in mind also.

4 DR. SNIDER: Thank you. Karen, on that
5 particular point --

6 DR. DAUM: Dr. Snider, is this on this very
7 point?

8 DR. SNIDER: Yes.

9 DR. DAUM: All right. Let's finish this
10 point. Go ahead. People are waiting in line so please
11 go ahead and finish this point.

12 DR. SNIDER: I just wanted to point out that
13 in the mathematical model yesterday this was taken into
14 account and they assumed the reason it was taken into
15 account is because women get infected with multiple
16 genotypes of HPV so that just because you're infected
17 with 16 or 18 and develop CIN 2 or 3 cervical cancer as
18 a result of that doesn't mean you are immune to.

19 It means, in fact, you're not immune to some
20 of the other oncogenic genotypes. There would be not
21 so much a replacement but there would be cervical cancer
22 in people who receive this vaccine as a result of their
23 being infected with other oncogen types if I understood
24 the model correctly. It's a small proportion but, I mean,
25 it's there.

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1 DR. GOLDENTHAL: I don't think I want to
2 comment on that model.

3 DR. DAUM: Let's go on then. Finally, Dr.
4 Reeves.

5 DR. SNIDER: I apologize.

6 DR. REEVES: I have two comments, one just a
7 follow-up on this. I would agree with everything that
8 Dr. Goldenthal said. I mean, I think there's not going
9 to be a rush of other types to replace it. If it works,
10 if there is an effect with 16 and 18 associated cancers,
11 then that gives us more evidence to make better vaccines.

12
13 I would agree with two endpoints. Actually,
14 I was unfortunately looking at the slide and I'm wondering
15 if we shouldn't discuss three. To me, CIN means
16 histologically confirmed disease and high-grade squamous
17 intraepithelial lesions means PAP smear diagnosed
18 disease.

19 I'm wondering since PAP smears are what, in
20 fact, women screen in on, are a relatively easy procedure
21 to do rather than following women all the time with
22 colposcopy and biopsy to get a CIN diagnosis whether,
23 in fact, studies should not have a large PAP smear
24 component and include obviously with colposcopic
25 follow-up but include reduction in high-grade squamous

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1 intraepithelial lesions as well as reduction in CIN 2/3
2 as well as potentially a decrease in infection or
3 persistence of shedding.

4 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Reeves.
5 My sense is that we've really had a fairly thorough sort
6 of go around in terms of issues that bear on question
7 1, the issue of endpoint choice.

8 So what I would like to do is take a short break.

9 Then upon return to begin systematically polling not
10 as a vote but systematically hearing from each member
11 of the panel in terms of the endpoint question. It's
12 10:25 here in the eastern time zone, or 10:20 according
13 to this green clock. We'll take a 15-minute break and
14 reassemble at 10:35.

15 (Whereupon, at 10:22 a.m. off the record until
16 10:39 a.m.)

17 DR. DAUM: Would everybody take their seats
18 and get ready? Thank you very much. We're missing a
19 few people and that's out of the table I must say. Do
20 you know where everybody is?

21 PARTICIPANT: No, but I'll go find them.

22 DR. DAUM: Okay. We are now going to sample
23 opinions, so to speak, on question 1. Before we do that,
24 Dr. Fleming has a couple of succinct unspoken points to
25 raise.

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1 Dr. Fleming.

2 DR. FLEMING: Thanks, Bob. I'll just keep
3 this to one theme, and that theme is we heard some brief
4 discussion at the beginning of this morning about as we're
5 struggling with defining which of these markers are really
6 the appropriate ones to use as surrogate or replacement
7 endpoints in accelerated approval or, for that matter,
8 even full approval we've noted that some of these markers,
9 certainly CIN 2/3, maybe even persistent infection,
10 influence how interventions or care is delivered.

11 There has been at least some uncertainty about
12 how that then impacts our view of the appropriateness
13 of those markers as surrogates.

14 I guess the point I want to make is it's not uncommon
15 in clinical practice in many disease settings for markers
16 to be used and their use can be in several different ways.

17
18 Markers can be used as prognostic factors to
19 guide patients and caregivers on risk of outcomes. They
20 can be used as triggers for when and how to intervene.

21 They can be used as surrogate endpoints which by
22 definition we should mean as endpoints that serve as
23 replacements for other ultimate more important clinical
24 endpoints.

25 The point that I want to make here is that those

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1 are three distinct purposes and it may be that some markers
2 are appropriate for some purposes and not others.

3 As a quick example, in the HIV world where we're
4 looking at interventions to prevent transmission of HIV,
5 it's clearly known that STDs are a prognostic factor
6 indicating higher risk for transmission of HIV. But that
7 doesn't mean that even though they are clearly prognostic
8 markers that they are appropriate surrogate markers.

9 A couple simple examples of this, there were
10 a couple of major trials done of STD inventions in
11 developing countries to look at whether we could prevent
12 transmission of HIV by preventing STDs. In the RICAH
13 trial with a mass intervention, we were successful in
14 reducing STDs but we had no impact on HIV.

15 Conversely in the MELANZA trial with syndromic
16 interventions we had no impact on a number of STDs but
17 we reduced HIV. You can readily have a prognostic factor.

18 Because it's a prognostic factor, that doesn't mean that
19 it's specifically a replacement endpoint or surrogate
20 endpoint.

21 It can also trigger an intervention. Classic
22 example, in cardiovascular diseases we know that
23 arrhythmias are risk factor for sudden death. It's
24 clearly a prognostic factor. For that reason, it
25 triggered many people to then use anti-arrhythmic

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1 interventions, echinide and flecunide, for example, to
2 reduce arrhythmias which they do do with the intention
3 of reducing sudden death.

4 Two hundred to 500,000 Americans a year were
5 using them on this premise. Ultimately a placebo
6 controlled trial was done that showed that they actually
7 did reduce arrhythmias but they tripled the death rate.

8
9 A marker that is clearly prognostic that may
10 trigger a physicians use to intervene doesn't necessarily
11 mean it's a reliable replacement measure to ultimately
12 judge the effect of the intervention on the clinical
13 endpoint.

14 The final example that I might give is early
15 HIV infection. We can treat early HIV infection using
16 HIV levels as a guide for how to tailor the intervention
17 and that may well be an appropriate strategy.

18 If you want to mix the types of anti-virals
19 we're using to achieve undetectable levels for an early
20 infected HIV person, but that doesn't at all mean that
21 reducing viral lows to undetectable levels in a certain
22 manner is a clear surrogate endpoint for achieving
23 prevention of long-term transmission of HIV, long-term
24 occurrence of systematic disease and death.

25 Ultimately what is important is that when we

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1 consider markers in a case like this, which would be
2 persistent infection, for example, or CIN 2/3 to
3 distinguish the fact that they are clearly prognostic.

4 We know that they are prognostic. They may
5 be used to trigger intervention. Certainly CIN 2/3 is.

6 But whether that makes them -- it doesn't at all address
7 whether the question that we're really interested in,
8 which is whether they are appropriate replacement
9 endpoints.

10 Although I will say -- certainly I will
11 acknowledge that if CIN 2/3 is a trigger for an invasive
12 surgical intervention, then a vaccine that would prevent
13 the need for that invasive surgical intervention, that
14 is a direct intrinsic value, but that doesn't also lead
15 to the additional conclusion that we're doing anything
16 specific relative to preventing cervical cancer.

17 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much. I think that
18 is a very clarifying and helpful perspective.

19 Dr. Snider, you wanted to speak to this very
20 issue?

21 DR. SNIDER: Actually, a very quick point that
22 is a little different, and that is that it was mentioned
23 to me at the break and sort of shamed me as an
24 epidemiologist that I hadn't brought this up earlier.
25 An FDA staff member by the name of Dr. Ellen Birch pointed

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1 out to me that in our discussion of concerns about
2 eradicating HPV 16 and 18 infections in individuals.

3 We didn't think about the secondary effects
4 of reducing the prevalence of those infections in the
5 populations and, therefore, even if there were certain
6 individuals who were not protected by the vaccine and
7 got cervical cancer, if we were able to reduce HPV
8 prevalence in the population by 80 percent or so, that
9 other people who were susceptible to cervical cancer from
10 this infection may not even acquire it because the
11 prevalence in the population had been reduced. I just
12 felt that it was an important point that needed to be
13 brought out in this consideration.

14 DR. DAUM: In other words, an effect in the
15 transmission perhaps.

16 DR. SNIDER: Yes.

17 DR. DAUM: You're absolutely right. It hasn't
18 been said and it sort of goes in the thinking of how
19 vaccines work when deployed over a whole population.

20 DR. SNIDER: And Sam points out the magnitude
21 of that would be greater if you gave it both to males
22 and females. Still I think even if you gave it to females
23 it would have some effect.

24 DR. DAUM: No, I think that it's good that it's
25 been said. I'm sure it's been on many of our thoughts

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1 as we go through.

2 I would like to sort thicken the soup a little
3 bit with raising one more issue. That is, this issue
4 of accelerated approval. What I think we can do is have
5 Karen Goldenthal remind us exactly what the agency means
6 by that which she has agreed to do during the break.

7 Then I think we can try going around and getting
8 everyone to speak to these issues to incorporate this
9 idea into your comments. I had thought initially we would
10 go around twice but I don't think we need to. If that
11 view needs to be reassessed, then I'm happy to reassess
12 it.

13 I think that given your choice of endpoints,
14 that you can also say how you would phase it in, how you
15 would advise the agency to phase it in to their strategy
16 for approving these vaccines.

17 In order to prepare us for this discussion,
18 I'm going to call on Karen first to remind us in very
19 precise succinct language, which she has agreed to do,
20 what exactly is meant by accelerated approval and how
21 it might phase into your choice of endpoints or multiple
22 endpoint scenario.

23 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Thank you. I have a couple
24 of points to make here. Accelerated approval is
25 basically the use of a surrogate marker that's reasonably

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1 likely to predict clinical benefit as the basis for an
2 approval, but that's not the end of it. You have to have
3 a confirmatory trial that would need to be well controlled
4 and well underway at the time of approval. I would even
5 think at the time of a BOA or license application
6 submission for the accelerated approval endpoint.

7 Just a few things to keep in mind in that regard.

8 This means that FDA would be asked to do an approval
9 based on interim data with the accelerated approval
10 application. That particular interim data would need
11 to be presented to an advisory committee. You need to
12 be thinking of how you would feel being an advisory
13 committee member and having that particular accelerated
14 approval endpoint to base your decision on.

15 Another critical thing pertains again to the
16 timing of the confirmatory trial, particularly with
17 regard to its completion. I think you need to think very
18 carefully about whether randomized trial could
19 realistically continue following an accelerated
20 approval.

21 My suspicion is that at least in the U.S. that
22 would be problematic. When I thought about applying
23 accelerated approval, as I mentioned yesterday, I thought
24 about the fact that it cuts about -- it would potentially
25 make the vaccine available maybe a year earlier than it

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1 would be otherwise thinking of the FDA review and approval
2 process.

3 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Karen.

4 Dr. Kohl, you have been placed at jeopardy by
5 Dr. Stephens' departure. I'm sorry about that.

6 What I would like to do is to ask each person
7 now, and we'll go around, to comment succinctly on the
8 two questions, that's 1 and 2. I would like you to see
9 if you could incorporate into your comments an issue that
10 the agency has raised and asked for your comment, and
11 that is the indication.

12 In other words -- I guess in other words, and
13 Karen Goldenthal, correct me if I don't understand it,
14 if there were an accelerated approval scenario where
15 something were approved based on an interim indication,
16 what would the approval indication say? I need you to
17 sort of put that into your comments as well.

18 Dr. Kohl, let's start with you and we'll just
19 get a feel for how this goes. We have a little over an
20 hour to do this and I think we can get it done.

21 Not quite yet. Clarifying comment.

22 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Also the indication. Our
23 question about what should the indication be also would
24 apply to traditional approval.

25 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Karen. One more bit of

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1 food to swallow.

2 DR. PALESE: And this is not a vote, correct?

3 DR. DAUM: This is not a vote. This is your
4 comment. They will be noted, recorded, and thought
5 about, I can assure you, line by line.

6 Dr. Kohl.

7 DR. KOHL: We are being asked to consider
8 endpoints for a vaccine that hopefully will provide
9 long-term, possibly lifelong protection against cancer.

10 The things that give me pause in terms of an early
11 surrogate, and I'm not sure what is distal and what is
12 proximal but in terms of a virological surrogate is we
13 have no idea what the duration or protection is yet for
14 any of these type vaccines. There's a
15 significant question about population heterogeneity and
16 detection in different types of populations which I think
17 needs to be addressed, or looked at, at least.

18 We don't have a clear definition of what
19 persistence of viral infection is yet from the experts,
20 although that may evolve in the next year or two possibly.

21 The considerations for size obviously have to include
22 what sample size and how long a duration would be necessary
23 for safety as well as some kind of efficacy in terms of
24 markers.

25 The last point that Karen brought up, early

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1 licensure, I think, will seriously preclude subsequent
2 studies of this vaccine, the hypothetical vaccine, and,
3 in fact, future vaccines for HPV prevention.

4 Bearing those issues in mind, what I would call
5 for in terms of primary efficacy is a CIN 2/3 model.
6 I would urge that this study be powered such that CIN
7 2/3 could be clearly defined in terms of efficacy, but
8 it would include sequential virology yearly or every six
9 months.

10 I'm not sure what is appropriate and what the
11 best technique will be at the time that this study is
12 undertaken. Right now it looks like it's PCR. I would
13 include definition of all oncogenic HPVs, not just the
14 ones that are in the vaccine so we can look at replacement.

15
16 And also would include immunological
17 parameters that would allow us to determine what the
18 correlates of protection are against both infection,
19 persistent infection, and CIN 2/3.

20 Given that as question No. 1, then I come to
21 is there something acceptable for me for accelerated
22 licensure.

23 If this study were to proceed as I envision
24 it, then for provisional licensure or accelerated
25 licensure I like something that Dr. Fleming suggested

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1 yesterday; namely, that my primary endpoint is going to
2 be CIN 2/3 efficacy but accelerated could be a proof that
3 there is a significant difference in CIN 2/3 between a
4 placebo and a control.

5 That is, as soon an interim analysis shows a
6 significant difference, accelerated approval might be
7 asked for, but in that study will obviously come efficacy.

8 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Kohl.
9 We're off and running. What you did that was really
10 wonderful is you actually managed to address all the
11 things I asked for and the agency asked for. If everybody
12 could sort of make a little checklist in their minds as
13 we go around to try and touch each of those points, I
14 think we'll have a wonderful discussion.

15 DR. KOHL: The only thing I didn't address,
16 I guess, would be what the package insert would say about
17 what this prevented. I think it would say prevention
18 against CIN 2/3 with probable effect on cervical cancer
19 but not proven.

20 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

21 Dr. Griffin.

22 DR. GRIFFIN: Okay. With respect to question
23 1, I guess my choices are A, B, and E. I think that I'm
24 of the opinion that if you prevent A, incident infection,
25 you will, therefore, by definition prevent persistent

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1 infection.

2 Now, whether you need then to -- and the main
3 objection to saying preventing incident infection is what
4 a criterion is for the efficacy of the vaccine and that
5 may be much too stringent. As many people have brought
6 up, you may get infection that is rapidly cleared and,
7 therefore, preventing persistent infection would be a
8 more realistic surrogate.

9 I think that data will just have to evolve so
10 if you required prevention of persistent infection, you
11 would accomplish that if you were also preventing incident
12 infection. Therefore, I guess B would be the main
13 virologic endpoint.

14 I guess I am most convinced by the one-year
15 endpoint for persistence, definition of persistence, but,
16 at the same time, realizing that this is a bell-shaped
17 curve, about when the actual oncogenic activities for
18 a virus infection would actually kick in for any
19 individual person you can't predict.

20 In some people that's going to happen early
21 and in some people that's going to happen late. In some
22 people that's not going to happen at all. There isn't
23 going to be any way to predict for an individual.

24 Then, lastly, I think that the outcome that's
25 most closely related to development of cervical cancer

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1 is the CIN 2/3 pathologic endpoint. What I would like
2 to see in a trial is imbedded both outcomes, that you
3 have two parameters.

4 Don't ask me how you would design this but I'm
5 convinced that it's happening with other kinds of
6 interventions with respect to HIV, etc., where you have
7 early endpoints that then allow early accelerated
8 approval, etc. But, at the same time, the same trial
9 has enough individuals in it that you follow them for
10 a longer period of time.

11 That's ongoing at the time that you're getting
12 your early outcome data and you avoid the problem of then
13 having to have a new trial with a vaccine that you've
14 now got approval for and one would say you ought to be
15 using. I would think that I would much favor a larger
16 trial to start out with that you look at both of these,
17 basically virologic and pathologic endpoint.

18 Embedded in that is then the fact that I can
19 see accelerated approval using a virologic endpoint,
20 i.e., persistent infection with the HPV types that are
21 in the vaccine. Then it's a little more problematic to
22 say what you are preventing.

23 You're not going to be able to say in the package
24 insert at that point that you are preventing cervical
25 carcinoma or even that you are preventing CIN 2/3 if you

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1 have that data yet. You may or may not be able to say
2 you are preventing infection depending on what the data
3 show.

4 If you actually have prevented infection, you
5 can say that with this oncogenic types. Otherwise, I
6 guess you're stuck with saying you are preventing
7 persistent infection if that's your outcome.

8 DR. DAUM: Diane, thank you very much.

9 Dixie, you're up.

10 DR. SNIDER: Thank you. First of all, I would
11 just like to congratulate everybody who's been involved
12 in all this work. I mean, it's really exciting to be
13 sitting around the table talking about a vaccine that
14 may prevent a cancer that globally and even in the United
15 States is of great significance. I would express my
16 appreciation to everybody in the academic community, NIH,
17 FDA, pharmaceutical companies and so forth for getting
18 us to this point.

19 As I expressed in my frustration yesterday,
20 it is a moving target and it does create a difficult
21 situation in terms of making definitive recommendations
22 but with the clarification that Karen gave us. I think
23 it is possible for us to address these questions, at least
24 as we view them today.

25 My recommendations are, I think, very similar

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1 to those who preceded me in that, at least at this point,
2 I would be interested in designing one trial that would
3 look at two endpoints, persistent infection and CIN 2/3.

4 I'm assuming, of course, if you're looking at persistent
5 infection, you're going to be looking at incident
6 infection but that wouldn't be a primary endpoint.

7 I do have some concerns about persistent
8 infection that others have already talked about as have
9 I. How is it going to be defined not only in terms of
10 the issues brought up there as it relates to the
11 appropriate number of tests in the interval between tests,
12 but the sampling methods and the assay methods and all
13 of that needs to be carefully worked out to be sure that
14 it's very highly sensitive in detecting the presence of
15 infection.

16 Then there's the whole issue of whatever you
17 want to call it, latent infection or an apparent infection
18 using techniques that aren't highly rigorous that concern
19 me. Those are issues that have to be dealt with.

20 With regard to the labeling, I guess I would
21 lean toward what Dr. Kohl, I think, has already mentioned,
22 that the label would say if this endpoint was reached
23 that the vaccine prevents CIN 2/3 which is associated
24 in a high proportion with the development of cervical
25 carcinoma.

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1 I personally would not be inclined to support
2 an accelerated approval approach right now. However,
3 right now that is two important words because there is
4 an evolving scientific database that might change my
5 opinion and obviously the opinion of many other people
6 if we got information.

7 We were able to get some information that, for
8 example, identified subgroups of women who clearly had
9 an extraordinarily high risk of cervical cancer or
10 progression to CIN 2 and 3 with persistent infection.
11 It's conceivable that somewhere along the way during this
12 trial that an alternative could be revisited.

13 But, at this point in time, I think there are enough
14 uncertainties about the significance of persistent
15 infection and how you define it that I would be a little
16 reticent to advise FDA and the manufacturer to proceed
17 along those lines and bring those data in. At least with
18 the database we have right now, I think it might not lead
19 to a happy outcome.

20 But if we were able to move to the point where
21 we became convinced that persistent infections or, at
22 least, persistent infections in certain identified
23 populations, whether that's personal characteristics,
24 viral loads, who knows what, really progressed to cancer,
25 then the labeling would be of this sort that the vaccine

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1 prevents persistent infection with these particular types
2 which is associated in some individuals, or maybe at that
3 point in time it could be a high proportion of individuals,
4 with progression to CIN 2 and 3 and cervical cancer.

5 DR. DAUM: Dixie, thank you very much.

6 Dr. Kim.

7 DR. KIM: I also support the concept that the
8 trial can be designed large enough to address perhaps
9 a minimum of two endpoints.

10 I guess this is in part that as we heard that
11 there are many issues that are not only heterogenous but
12 also answers are not in our hand at this time so that
13 I think it is important to be able to monitor all the
14 issues which have been addressed during this meeting as
15 part of perhaps a trial so that, again, going back to
16 the specific questions would be my preference would be
17 looking to a persistent HPV infection as a primary
18 endpoint since the HPV infection per se can be difficult
19 to predict whether you regress or you persist.

20 I would at least like to see that a vaccine
21 has been shown to be beneficial in preventing persistent
22 HPV infection due to vaccine types.

23 Then I guess the question which we do not have
24 based on the discussion is whether that can be translated
25 into the bottom line which is reduction in cervical

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1 cancer. I think it's because of that I would certainly
2 like to see some data related to those issues as the study
3 is coming along.

4 Particularly I would like to see the
5 information on CIN 2 and 3. Again, I think cervical
6 cancer would be very, very difficult to achieve as an
7 endpoint so CIN 2 and 3 as a secondary endpoint as part
8 of a trial.

9 So what that means, at least to me, is that
10 when this vaccine can go through and then would be
11 presented as an accelerated format, then I would like
12 to see that vaccine has shown to be beneficial in
13 significant reduction of persistent HPV infection due
14 to serotypes.

15 Also, I would like to see that time of
16 discussion, some information on a significant reduction
17 on CIN 2 and 3 as a sort of assurance that, indeed,
18 prevention of persistent infection has, indeed, a sort
19 of right kind of target that we all want to see as part
20 of this vaccine.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Kim.

22 Dr. Katz.

23 DR. KATZ: I don't think I have any
24 disagreement with what my preceding colleagues have
25 stated. To me the most important issues or endpoints

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1 would be persistent infection and the CIN 2/3.

2 But I have several questions which perhaps are
3 tangential but I would like to see some nested studies
4 within the large trial and some nested studies that in
5 a smaller cohort might be able to answer some of the
6 questions we've tossed about to which we don't have answer
7 about, the role of mucosal or secretory antibody, the
8 role of salmeated infection and what could be done in
9 looking at that along with virus cultures.

10 The other issue that concerns me is the way
11 we've conducted conventional vaccine studies, and I would
12 call this one somewhat unconventional, is once you've
13 reached a point where you're comfortable that you've
14 achieved your goals, the controls then receive the vaccine
15 that the original recipients have the benefit of.

16 I don't know when you would feel you've reached
17 that point. If we accept the endpoints of persistent
18 infection and CIN 2/3, then maybe that's the time that
19 you would give the controls the vaccine. But
20 that wouldn't answer what Dr. Kim wants which is the next
21 step which is cervical cancer. I think I would have to
22 consider that in my overall format as I have put together
23 the longitudinal protocol.

24 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Katz.

25 Dr. Faggett.

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1 DR. FAGGETT: I disconnected my phone.

2 DR. DAUM: I'm very grateful.

3 DR. FAGGETT: I really learned a lot these past
4 couple days. Just sitting next to Dr. Katz is always
5 an hallucinating experience.

6 Really, I think more of us primary care
7 providers need to hear this kind of very high-level
8 discussion of the science of the vaccine approval process.

9 I think it would make us better able to discuss it with
10 our patients and encourage them to get the immunizations
11 available.

12 I think question No. 1, I agree with previous
13 speakers. Again, it would appear that persistent
14 infection in CIN 2/3 consensus endpoints, the accelerated
15 approval I think we should do it. I think we should have
16 as long as possible.

17 It would appear that the longer we go, the more
18 evidence we'll have in terms of the efficacy in preventing
19 cancer. I would just say I concur with previous speakers
20 with those comments.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you. I need to press you a
22 little bit, though. The accelerated approval, where do
23 you sit on that?

24 DR. FAGGETT: Yes. I think we should have
25 accelerated approval.

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1 DR. DAUM: The endpoint you pick would be?
2 I just want to make sure I'm very clear on what you're
3 saying.

4 DR. FAGGETT: Again, as previous speakers,
5 that you would prevent the disease. I think the longer
6 you go the more evidence you will have that you can prevent
7 cancer so I would say it would be probable prevention
8 of cancer would be an endpoint.

9 DR. DAUM: Which endpoint would you pick? Did
10 I miss it? Did you say it? If you did, I apologize.
11 Persistent infection?

12 DR. FAGGETT: Right. Persistent infection.

13 DR. DAUM: Okay.

14 DR. FAGGETT: I said persistent and CIN 2/3.

15 DR. DAUM: So you picked two different ones.

16 DR. FAGGETT: Yeah, those two.

17 DR. DAUM: I apologize. You want two
18 different endpoints?

19 DR. FAGGETT: Right.

20 DR. DAUM: I think we know what you want now.

21 Ms. Fisher?

22 MS. FISHER: I thought of this in two
23 separately so I'm making two separate statements.

24 DR. DAUM: Stop for one second. You said
25 something that upset Dr. Mitthune.

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1 DR. MITTHUNE: Just to clarify, Dr. Faggett,
2 would you want both the virology and the CIN 2/3 for
3 accelerated approval or would you want only the virology
4 on regular approval? You want both? Thank you.

5 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Mitthune. Thank
6 you, Dr. Faggett. Thank you, Dr. Katz.

7 Now, Ms. Fisher.

8 MS. FISHER: Well, first I'm going to speak
9 about the endpoints. From the information that was
10 presented to us in both closed and open sessions of this
11 meeting, it appears that if an HPV vaccine demonstrated
12 prevention of persistent HPV infection with certain types
13 such as HPV 16 and 18, it would suggest that it would
14 be effective in preventing cervical cancer associated
15 with those types.

16 However, much appears to be unknown about
17 potential cofactors involved and why some women clear
18 HPV infection and some do not and go on to develop cervical
19 cancer. I think there needs to be more known about these
20 potential cofactors because they may be important
21 independent of HPV infection.

22 In prelicensure clinical trials demonstrating
23 efficacy, the standard used should include follow-up of
24 all participants to prove not only prevention of
25 persistent HPV infection, but also prevention of CIN 2/3

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1 as well as prevention of cervical cancer because CIN 2/3
2 is a more certain predictor that cancer will most likely
3 occur and demonstration of prevention of cervical cancer
4 is the only way the vaccine user could be reasonably
5 confident that it is, indeed, a vaccine that could prevent
6 cervical cancer.

7 The other statement is on the accelerated
8 approval process. I think, needless to say, certainly
9 cervical cancer is a terrible disease for women,
10 especially in developing countries and we need safe and
11 effective ways to prevent it.

12 Because the majority of women clear HPV
13 infection and a very small number go on to develop
14 persistent infection, and an even smaller number go on
15 to develop cervical cancer, I'm concerned about an
16 accelerated approval process for licensure.

17 If the request for accelerated approval was
18 for an HPV vaccine that would only be used by women known
19 to be at very high risk for developing cervical cancer,
20 then I might feel differently.

21 However, this discussion has been about an HPV
22 vaccine that would target all healthy adolescent girls
23 and adult women, perhaps even female and male children.

24 That's entirely another matter. We need to have a better
25 understanding of the biological mechanisms of long-term

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1 immunity of HPV infection.

2 We need more information about safety including
3 the potential ability of this protein vaccine to induce
4 autoimmunity in a subset of genetically susceptible
5 individuals, as well as the potential negative impact
6 on women with preexisting HPV infection.

7 Clearly it should not be an a priori assumption
8 that this vaccine has no long-term negative health
9 consequences whatsoever. Long-term studies need to be
10 done to measure for all morbidity and mortality outcomes.

11
12 I'm not talking about paying attention to car
13 crashes and ski accidents that occur during the study
14 but taking serious development of post-vaccination
15 deterioration of health such as multiple sclerosis-like
16 symptoms, arthralgia, arthritis, thyroid disease, etc.,
17 as well as exacerbation of preexisting autoimmune
18 conditions during long-term follow-up.

19 If we don't ask for these kinds of studies
20 prelicensure, an unknown number of young women who may
21 indeed avoid infection with HPV and cervical cancer by
22 using an HPV vaccine could be left with other vaccine
23 induced chronic health problems because the vaccine was
24 licensed too quickly without enough data. I do not think
25 the accelerated approval process is appropriate for this

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1 vaccine.

2 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Fisher.

3 Dr. Palese.

4 DR. PALESE: This is obviously a very complex
5 issue here. Human papilloma virus we don't have a good
6 system, no good animal model, and certainly no antivirals
7 and no vaccines. On the other hand, cervical cancer
8 appears to be almost 100 percent associated with infection
9 by HPV.

10 Now, if we have a vaccine which basically
11 prevents infection and we can't demonstrate virus, I'm
12 sort of persuaded by persistent HPV as an endpoint and
13 I would go along with Dr. Lowy's recommendation of a year.

14 I guess he meant two assays. He didn't give a specific
15 amount because of an interval but I think six months may
16 be okay.

17 Clearly as a virologist I feel if there is no
18 virus, then there is no disease so this is really for
19 me very, very compelling that one would be able to prevent
20 infection and replication of the virus that this must
21 have some consequences and that's why I feel very
22 comfortable with an endpoint which measures persistent
23 HPV infections.

24 And having that rationale, I sort of also feel
25 that an accelerated approach would be -- I would support

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1 that. Accelerated approval I would support,
2 particularly if there is a provision for a long-term
3 analysis in there and that the time would be large enough
4 in terms of measuring other parameters. Again, I would
5 be happy enough if it turns out that there is no virus
6 replication that we would vote for an accelerated
7 approach.

8 In terms of the labeling I would also say if
9 the vaccine prevents infection, then it is also most
10 likely prevents cervical cancer so I would be quite happy
11 with that kind of labeling.

12 DR. DAUM: Dr. Goldenthal, if I understood you,
13 the accelerated approval scenario would be one that would
14 be granted by the agency only if there were a confirmatory
15 trial in progress or enrollment was completed. Is that
16 correct?

17 DR. GOLDENTHAL: That's the way accelerated
18 approval ordinarily works, yes.

19 DR. DAUM: So, Dr. Palese, let me come back
20 to you for just one moment. You mentioned that you would
21 have accelerated approval based on viral persistence,
22 if I understood you.

23 DR. PALESE: Yes.

24 DR. DAUM: And if that's the case, then you
25 would accept that caveat that the confirmatory trial be

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1 in progress but I didn't hear you say that.

2 DR. PALESE: Yes, with the same endpoint. I
3 mean, I'm not -- maybe I didn't understand your question.

4
5 DR. DAUM: Okay. Agency people listen and if
6 I'm not saying it right, please jump in. It seems to
7 me that you might ask for traditional approval with
8 persistent viral infection as your endpoint.

9 DR. PALESE: No, that's not what I am --

10 DR. DAUM: Right. And then accelerated
11 approval though would have to have an interim endpoint
12 that approval would be granted for but a confirmatory
13 trial in progress or underway as well for the
14 agency --

15 DR. PALESE: What kind of endpoints? I mean,
16 that's the question. For this confirmatory trial that's
17 --

18 DR. DAUM: That's what we're asking you to
19 comment on.

20 DR. PALESE: Okay. I will be happy with
21 persistent -- if there's no virus, there's no disease
22 so I will be happy with the confirmatory trial with the
23 same endpoint of persistent HPV.

24 DR. DAUM: Does that fit with agency guidelines
25 or are we okay with that?

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1 DR. GOLDENTHAL: It almost sounded like he's
2 more advocating traditional approval.

3 DR. DAUM: I think so, yeah. With persistent
4 viral infection as the endpoint. I think that's what
5 he's saying.

6 DR. PALESE: So what am I saying?

7 DR. DAUM: I'll be damned if I know.

8 DR. PALESE: I will keep going for an
9 accelerated approval. If that requires a confirmatory
10 trial going on, I would support that but with the
11 assumption that the endpoint again would be persistent
12 infection.

13 DR. DAUM: Okay. I understand what you're
14 saying and it doesn't completely gel for me but that's
15 okay. And the indication would be what?

16 DR. PALESE: That a vaccine, if it turns out
17 that it really prevents infection, most likely prevents
18 infection to a certain percentage and, therefore, is most
19 likely to prevent also cervical cancer.

20 DR. DAUM: Very good. Thank you.

21 Dr. Myers.

22 DR. MYERS: The endpoint of interest is
23 cervical cancer and I think the data on CIN 2 and 3 as
24 a part of the natural history is sufficiently robust that
25 it predicts a clinical benefit directly I think is clear

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1 and it probably serves as a surrogate for cervical cancer.

2 While I agree with a lot of the preceding
3 comments, it's intuitive that prevention of infection,
4 and specifically prevention of persistent infection even
5 without dislogic changes, it's intuitive that those could
6 be endpoints. I don't think the data at this time are
7 sufficiently robust. Like somebody said previously, at
8 this time that is a qualifier.

9 I think some of the data we heard in closed
10 session yesterday may imply that a year from now or so
11 we may be able to say that persistent infection, in fact,
12 in the absence of histology could be a marker but it's
13 not at this point. I would suggest that infection are
14 secondary endpoints and not the primary endpoint.

15 I would want data on the other high-risk HPVs
16 as well looking for emergence of those. But also because
17 I think for the next generation of vaccines that will
18 be very important.

19 Going back to the secondary endpoint, the
20 infection endpoints, I think, are also critical to collect
21 that now as part of the study so that the next generation
22 of vaccines we will, in fact, know whether we can utilize
23 these as surrogate markers for the histology.

24 I mentioned this before a couple times. I
25 would just like to say it again. I think it is important

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1 to understand that it will be important to examine the
2 outcomes on an intent to humanize perspective.

3 I think to look just at HPV 16 and 18, naive
4 individuals, would be a mistake and that we need to
5 understand what immunization of previously infected young
6 women is as to whether that reduces the risk of persistent
7 infection or has an adverse outcome because this vaccine
8 will not be directed just at naive individuals. It will
9 be targeted to specifically young women who are at high
10 risk and, therefore, may already be infected.

11 As to accelerated approval, I'm unable to
12 support that conceptually in that I think it would be
13 very difficult to complete a study even if enrollment
14 is completed. Once the vaccine is approved and is being
15 marketed, I think it would be very difficult for the
16 placebo arm to be maintained. Therefore, as I think the
17 definitive endpoint is CIN 2/3, then I think it would
18 be very difficult to support an accelerated approval.

19 With that said, I think if, in fact, early on
20 in the process there were a significant difference between
21 the groups for CIN 2 and 3 before the full duration of
22 the study is completed, then I would consider accelerated
23 approval at that point.

24 From the labeling perspective I thought Steve
25 Kohl and Dixie said it quite well and I would agree with

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1 that.

2 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Marty.

3 Dr. McInnes.

4 DR. McINNES: My certainty and uncertainty
5 about papilloma viral infections and their relationship
6 to cancer and the role of this vaccine waxed and waned.

7 I think I'm left here with a fair amount of certainty
8 that we are reasonably uncertain about lots of things
9 here.

10 I'm moving forward on the assumptions that
11 human papilloma virus infection is necessary for and does
12 precede cervical cancer, although it's not sufficiently
13 causal. I do understand that HPV infection with the
14 oncogenic type is much more common than the resulting
15 cancers.

16 Nevertheless, I'm also reasonably comfortable
17 with the assumption that persistent infection is linked
18 to risk of CIN 2, CIN 3, and invasive cancer.

19 With the reality of having to accept a
20 surrogate, I am comfortable with persistent infection
21 as an endpoint, surrogate endpoint. The timing of that,
22 I am somewhat concerned about the short interval that
23 has been proposed.

24 Given the data that incident infections may
25 clear within eight months, I am bothered by time frames

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1 that are less than that. I think I envision protracted
2 trials rather than condensed trials.

3 I am somewhat persuaded that cytologic
4 abnormalities are an endpoint for consideration in the
5 trials because they certainly would give us a sense of
6 the bad player HPV infections with more rapid progression
7 to the CIN 2 and CIN 3.

8 I do not dismiss the role of cytological
9 evaluation. Certainly it's a question of where it would
10 be within the framework of endpoints, primary, secondary,
11 tertiary endpoints.

12 The case definitions, I think I'm not totally
13 resolved on which of the spectrum of clinical disease
14 has a place and which doesn't. At this point I'm not
15 persuaded that any of the spectrum doesn't have a
16 potential place in articulation of an endpoint. I would
17 leave open the possibility of a spectrum of clinical
18 disease being incorporated with persistent viral
19 infection into the endpoint.

20 Regarding the accelerated approval, I at this
21 time am having a great deal of pragmatic difficulty
22 understanding how sufficient safety data, how a
23 considerable safety database will be brought to bear for
24 consideration for the accelerated approval.

25 Pragmatically when I lay out a time frame I

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1 don't at this point see much to be gained. I'm obviously
2 open to being persuaded of something other than that.
3 At this point I am advocating a traditional approval and
4 I'm having difficulty understanding the role of
5 accelerated approval for this vaccine.

6 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much. Quite clear.

7 Dr. Reeves.

8 DR. REEVES: Okay. To begin, I would be in
9 favor of accelerated licensure because of the nature of
10 the disease and the long time period and actually seeing
11 the disease of interest. The disease of interest is
12 prevention of cervical cancer.

13 For that reason I believe studies should be
14 done in high-risk populations, the woman that actually
15 get cervical cancer in the United States, and to the extent
16 possible so that one can begin early on. They should
17 involve populations that have cancer registry so that
18 a long-term effect can be seen.

19 I think the only appropriate surrogate
20 endpoint, and perhaps an endpoint in and of itself is
21 CIN 2/3. In the United States in terms of body count
22 that is actually the primary cost, the primary morbidity.

23 If treatments for that could be cut down significantly,
24 it would be a significant public health advance so I think
25 that is a very appropriate endpoint -- surrogate endpoint

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1 or endpoint.

2 I believe that the virology and immunology are
3 also terribly important to studies and must be included
4 as either co-surrogate endpoints or data that must be
5 measured. I really don't have an opinion on what
6 persistent infection is.

7 I think that viral studies must be very
8 complete. The patients, or the subjects, should be
9 followed by cytology as well. Every time that a cytologic
10 sample is taken, a virologic sample taken also.
11 Presumably high-grade SIL will go down but the patients
12 with low-grade SIL, their virology is the important
13 comparison along with the placebos.

14 Cervical immunology is terribly important to
15 this and I believe should be included in any of the
16 studies. I think the question of incident HPV infection
17 is probably going to be an impossible one to address.

18 I think the term is used wrong. The first
19 culture positive is not an incident disease. It's the
20 first incident infection. It's the first infection in
21 a person that has not been infected with the agent
22 previously.

23 I think it's going to be impossible to cover
24 in the studies but it's been brought up a couple times.
25 One of the primary epidemiologic risk factors is age

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1 at first intercourse. That group of women in the
2 high-risk group is going to be part of this but only a
3 small part of it.

4 As far as the package insert, I believe it's
5 premature to be discussing that.

6 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Reeves.
7 Dr. Goldberg.

8 DR. GOLDBERG: Thank you. I think that the
9 accelerated approval --

10 DR. DAUM: Sorry. We may have a procedural
11 problem.

12 DR. MITTHUNE: I would just like to ask for
13 a clarification, Dr. Reeves. You said that you thought
14 that CIN 2/3 would be your basis for accelerated approval?

15 DR. REEVES: That's correct.

16 DR. MITTHUNE: What would be your confirmatory
17 study endpoint?

18 DR. REEVES: My confirmatory study? I think
19 CIN 2/3 in and of itself would be sufficient. I think
20 that's an important enough public health problem that
21 if that could be dramatically reduced, I would be quite
22 happy. I think cervical cancer is going to take decades
23 which is, in fact, the final end product.

24 DR. MITTHUNE: Right. So are you actually
25 advocating a traditional approval based on CIN 2/3 as

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1 your endpoint?

2 DR. REEVES: That's correct, with obviously
3 evaluation of the virologic and immunologic data that
4 is collected along with it.

5 DR. MITTHUNE: Thank you. One further
6 clarification. Dr. McInnes, you said that you did not
7 support and you advocated a traditional approval. It
8 wasn't clear to me what endpoint would support that
9 traditional approval.

10 DR. McINNES: I would use vaccine type DNA
11 persistence so viral persistence. I talked about some
12 spectrum of clinical presentation ranging from vaccine
13 type DNA positive, cytological abnormalities to some
14 clinical endpoint. I'm not opposed to the CIN 2/3. I'm
15 just considering that it may need to be broader.

16 DR. MITTHUNE: Thank you.

17 DR. DAUM: Thank you.

18 Before we go to Dr. Goldberg, Dr. Goldenthal,
19 I think there's a little bit of confusion still about
20 accelerated approval. I would like you to just say the
21 sentences you said before so that the remaining committee
22 members can have it straight. What does accelerated
23 approval mean?

24 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Okay. Accelerated approval
25 means that you would have, I guess, a drug development

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1 plan in place where a product would be initially approved,
2 receive the accelerated approval based on a surrogate
3 and, at the same time, there would be a confirmatory
4 efficacy trial that was also well controlled and well
5 under way at the time of license application submission.

6
7 This would mean, again, a committee and FDA
8 would have to review the interim data. That interim data
9 could be used for the accelerated approval. Then we would
10 be very interested in the timing, of course, of the
11 confirmatory trial and when it would be completed in
12 comparison to when the license application was submitted.

13 You can have -- you know, we've heard various scenarios.

14
15 One thing that was mentioned was, I guess, sort
16 of an early look at CIN 2/3 and then those people might
17 be followed for another year. You might get more
18 follow-up data on other participants in the trial. That
19 was one example of the sort of accelerated approval.
20 In that case, it was the same endpoint.

21 Usually you think of a different -- when I've
22 seen it used in other context, it's been usually two
23 endpoints, one for accelerated approval and one for the
24 confirmatory trial endpoint which is something different.

25 Perhaps we can work in the CIN 2/3 for both.

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1 DR. GEBER: I just wanted to add that maybe
2 a way of thinking of it that the accelerated approval
3 is in a way a preliminary approval and if that were
4 granted, the sponsor would have to then meet their
5 endpoint in the confirmatory trial to keep their approval.

6 If one decided that a persistent infection was an
7 endpoint for a confirmatory trial, or if one were not
8 satisfied for an endpoint for a traditional approval,
9 then that would be a preliminary approval.

10 DR. DAUM: Question about this?

11 DR. FELIX: Procedure.

12 DR. DAUM: Please go ahead.

13 DR. FELIX: If in the confirmatory trial does
14 it have to be a failure to achieve significance or would
15 it -- I'm sorry. Would it have to achieve significance
16 or failure to achieve significance? Would that belie
17 the preliminary approval gain at accelerated?

18 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Certainly we can withdraw
19 approval if the confirmatory trial is a failure, so to
20 speak. In other words, if they don't find a significant
21 result, than we can withdraw the approval. We do have
22 that authority.

23 DR. DAUM: Dixie and Steve, we need to hear
24 from the other half of the table.

25 DR. SNIDER: I think they need to understand

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1 the question.

2 DR. DAUM: Right to this point. Go ahead but
3 we're running behind. Go ahead, Dixie, and then Steve.

4 DR. SNIDER: My question is that, if I
5 understand correctly then, under accelerated approval
6 the product would be licensed and available and,
7 therefore, the individuals who participated in the
8 confirmatory trial would have to be informed about the
9 availability of the vaccine and presumably the IRBs would
10 require that is included in the consent form and the IRBs
11 would have to approve such a trial.

12 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Right. That actually speaks
13 to my major concern which is continuing the trial
14 following approval. I don't believe that there is a major
15 issue in continuing a trial during the FDA review of the
16 BLA.

17 As I have said, I think that accelerated
18 approval might buy you a year but it's still got to be
19 -- that's a very good question. Would an IRB concur with,
20 you know, an ongoing placebo-controlled trial following
21 approval. In the U.S. that's pretty unlikely.

22 DR. HILDESHEIM: If I could provide some
23 factual information.

24 DR. DAUM: Tell us who you are and your
25 affiliation.

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1 DR. HILDESHEIM: Allan Hildesheim with the
2 National Cancer Institute. If we did any interim
3 analysis to submit to the FDA, we would have to present
4 it to our IRB data and safety monitoring board.

5 We've discussed this and it's clear that any
6 trial that had early CIN 2/3 as an accelerated outcome
7 with confirmatory long-term CIN 2/3 would not happen
8 because we would vaccinate our placebo group at the
9 instant that we saw any evidence of protection against
10 CIN 2/3.

11 DR. DAUM: Other the other hand --

12 DR. HILDESHEIM: Possibly even persistent
13 infection.

14 DR. DAUM: On the other hand, if the first basis
15 for interim approval were some viral marker like viral
16 persistence and there was an indication for viral
17 persistence and the trial were ongoing to look at CIN
18 2/3 or cervical cancer, that trial wouldn't necessarily
19 have to be aborted because the vaccine would be available
20 for prevention of viral infection. IRB
21 would certainly have to address that and it's hard to
22 know how it would come out. It's not as clear as the
23 example you gave where it's very clear an IRB shouldn't
24 go along with it if they were willing to even.

25 DR. HILDESHEIM: You are correct, it's more

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1 murky. However, my sense from the discussions I've had
2 with IRB and DSMB members for our trial is that if we
3 showed something was protected against persistent
4 infection for a reasonable amount of time, that we may
5 not have to abort the trial but we would be required
6 ethnically to inform all of the women.

7 If they wanted, they could withdraw from the
8 trial. In effect, any follow-up data after that would
9 be highly biased by who stayed and decided not to stay
10 in the trial.

11 DR. DAUM: Perhaps. I think that's very
12 helpful. I think we understand what accelerated approval
13 means and I'm really anxious to hear from this side of
14 the table so let's go on.

15 DR. GOLDBERG: I'm not sure I know anymore but
16 I believe there can be a well-designed trial for vaccine
17 efficacy based on the CIN 2/3 or worse including any cases
18 of cervical cancer that would be included in that
19 endpoint.

20 With that said, I do believe you have to monitor
21 for persistent HPV and the length of the interval has
22 to be studied. I guess from everything we've heard so
23 far, probably a year is the interval.

24 What I would suggest as an interim analysis
25 for CIN 2/3 efficacy requiring that persistent -- that

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1 the endpoint is supported at that interim analysis if
2 there was a recommendation to stop the trial early with
3 the persistent HPV also showing efficacy.

4 I believe that we should be studying this in
5 high-risk populations as well. I think there should be
6 some stratification and HPV positive at entry should be
7 retained as a stratum file so that you will have some
8 information on possibly higher risk women.

9 The length of the study is an issue. It could
10 be a much longer study than was anticipated, but I don't
11 believe that even if we did a vaccine efficacy trial with
12 persistence as the endpoint that we would ever be able
13 to complete a confirmatory trial.

14 I think we have to make the effort to expand
15 both enrollment initially and lengthening the follow-up
16 but having a carefully planned interim analysis or interim
17 analyses based on the best available planning mechanism
18 that you can put in place.

19 I also think that there needs to be a mechanism
20 in place for the long-term follow-up for the occurrence
21 of untoward events as well as cancer. You also during
22 the trial should be monitoring for other types of CIN
23 2/3 and/or cervical cancer associated with other types
24 of HPV than just 16 and 18 to be able to assess the impact
25 of this on that.

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1 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Could you just clarify are
2 you advocating CIN 2/3 for traditional approval?

3 DR. GOLDBERG: Traditional approval.

4 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Okay.

5 DR. GOLDBERG: I don't believe accelerated
6 approval is really possible here. But I do believe that
7 if the trial were well designed and the results compelling
8 somewhere during that trial, there could be an early
9 stopping but there still needs to be follow-up for safety.

10 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Goldberg.

11 Dr. Fleming.

12 DR. FLEMING: Thank you. Clearly the
13 prevention of cervical cancer is a critically important
14 public health problem and that leads to an obvious need
15 for effective, responsible, and timely evaluation of
16 various vaccines here for targeting the risk or for
17 targeting the reduction and the risk of cervical cancer.

18 However, the use of surrogates has always
19 raised complex issues. There is clearly a tradeoff when
20 we're using surrogates between the timeliness and the
21 reliability of conclusions. In this specific setting
22 what we have in hand is strong evidence that HPV infection
23 is a necessary factor.

24 But there is significant uncertainty from the
25 information we have at this point regarding whether

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1 reduction in various virologic, cytologic, and histologic
2 markers and what duration of effects on those markers
3 translates into being reasonably likely to predict
4 benefit which is the condition put forward before us by
5 the FDA.

6 To me this leads us to the wisdom that Steve
7 Kohl had pointed out yesterday, "When in doubt, be
8 cautious." I think there is a lot of doubt in this
9 setting. I think there is additional reasons to be
10 cautious. Dr. Fisher pointed out how broadly this
11 vaccine is going to be used. To my way of thinking, that
12 does mean this is a setting where we have to be cautious.

13 I'm also concerned that the trials that lead
14 to the initial approvals have a particular burden to be
15 well designed. It's going to be extremely difficult in
16 the future. You won't be looking at future vaccines
17 addressed through placebo-controlled trials. Inferior
18 trials will be even that much more problematic.

19 All of this leads me to being very cautious.

20 My sense is from what we've heard the marker that has
21 the strongest evidence for reliability, even though it,
22 too, is not fully reliable, is CIN 2/3 and, in particular,
23 CIN 3.

24 My sense here, as I think through the two
25 stages, Bob, in this accelerated approval leading to full

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1 approval, ultimately the full approval from my
2 perspective needs to have considerable evidence that
3 we're influencing CIN 2/3 in two ways here. One is
4 relative to the targeted types of HPV 16 and 18.

5 I think we need to be ruling out 33 or 50 percent
6 reductions. We need to have sufficient evidence that
7 we have something on the order of an 80 percent reduction
8 that we can rule out 33 to 50 percent reductions.
9 Relative to untargeted types, I would argue that we need
10 to have evidence that over all we're seeing a reduction
11 in CIN 2/3.

12 Ultimately the data that we would have in hand
13 in the final approval, I think, has to address all of
14 the dimensions of strength of evidence, breath of effect,
15 and durability of effect.

16 Now, working backwards could we do an
17 accelerated approval? I think this is very
18 controversial. I think there is a potential here for
19 doing an accelerated approval.

20 Just to give you a sense of what I'm thinking,
21 the type of trial that I think can address what I would
22 think we would need for an accelerated and for full
23 approval is one that might only involve
24 -- I say only in contrast to what would be in some settings
25 even bigger trials, 10,000 to 15,000 participants in a

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1 two-arm trial where they would take a year of accrual
2 and about three years of follow-up to get what I'm getting
3 at here for the accelerated approval target and an
4 additional two to three years of follow-up for the full
5 approval, essentially what could be the accelerated
6 approval.

7 If we had significant evidence of a reduction
8 in targeted HPV 16 to 18 type CIN 2/3, that would take
9 on the order of 20 to 25 specific cases. The problem
10 with that is what we may be seeing with that is simply
11 the ability of the vaccine to reduce this risk of
12 progression to CIN 2/3 in the rapid progressors which
13 may not represent a more global effect.

14 For that reason I would strongly support that
15 there would be a dual endpoint in the accelerated approval
16 that would be based on persistent infection, specifically
17 persistent HPV 16/18 infection.

18 I'm not comfortable at this moment, though,
19 defining over what interval. I think there is a lot that
20 is unknown, although the good news is in the course of
21 finalizing the design and implementing these trials,
22 there will be some additional time to tap into natural
23 history data.

24 What I would specifically focus on here is
25 getting additional data from prospective cohorts that

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1 allows us to follow up incident cases that are going to
2 allow us to understand more clearly what will be the time
3 of persistent infection as well as potentially viral
4 loads. This could be multi-variate. What is
5 the duration of persistent infection and level of viral
6 burden that translates into fairly reliable evidence that
7 when these markers are achieved, there is going to be
8 a high level of risk of progression of CIN 2/3.

9 The reason I want this as part of the
10 accelerated approval evidence is that if an accelerated
11 approval is going to be based on 25 cases relating to
12 CIN 2/3 which is all it takes to rule out quality when
13 you have an 80 percent reduction, I want to have additional
14 evidence to give me a sense that when I'm going to get
15 more durable evidence later on about more global effects
16 on CIN 2/3, that this is going to be achieved and that
17 is where I think the added data on persistent infection
18 as a co-marker for accelerated approval is complimentary
19 in its insight.

20 What I haven't mentioned is there's a third
21 dimension I would ask for to be explored in the accelerated
22 approval. In addition to persistent infection where you
23 are going to define much better than we can today exactly
24 what that is after you follow these incident cohorts,
25 I would like to see the CIN 2/3, HPV 16/18.

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1 I would also like to see consideration of need
2 for reduction in invasive therapies because that is, in
3 fact, part of the tangible benefit that is going to be
4 achieved here.

5 Where I would define invasive therapy,
6 certainly what I'm thinking are of, for example, what
7 typically would be clinical care when you have a CIN 2/3
8 infection, diagnostic decisional procedures,
9 electro-loop excisions, for example.

10 Interventions which by their very nature have
11 such clinical importance that it exceeds the cost
12 inconvenience and toxicities and side effects of the very
13 intervention, i.e., the vaccine you're going to be
14 delivering to prevent these. They have to be significant
15 events.

16 Now, with this as an accelerated approval, what
17 we don't have, just to repeat what I said earlier, in
18 my view is adequate insight about strength of evidence,
19 breathe of effect, and duration of effect.

20 Ultimately this trial would need to continue
21 and I'm guessing to approximately a six-year median
22 follow-up point to be able to have sufficient evidence
23 to rule out a 33 to 50 percent reduction, that we have
24 even a better effect than that.

25 If we have an 80 percent true reduction, it's

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1 going to take 40 to 60 events to do this. If we have
2 at least an 80 percent reduction on targeted HPV 16 to
3 18 based on Karen's projections, that's going to translate
4 into about a 50 percent global reduction. At
5 the same time this trial is going to be powered to rule
6 out no reduction. My standard for untargeted CIN 2/3
7 is to at least conclude that you are achieving this roughly
8 50 percent reduction ruling out no reduction.

9 But for targeted 16/18 I want to see an 80
10 percent reduction ruling out 33 to 50 percent combined
11 with the additional evidence that invasive interventions
12 are also being reduced.

13 Final comment. Is this doable? My sense is
14 this is a strategy of about a 10,000 to 15,000 person
15 trial. We're going to be about four years into this trial
16 when we would have this information that I outlined for
17 the accelerated approval. We're still about three years
18 away from having the final data.

19 There will be certainly a lag time of
20 approximately a year from the time the data are
21 essentially realized and when they would be analyzed,
22 presented, and reviewed for regulatory approval which
23 essentially would mean if at that point the vaccine was
24 now available for potential access to the control arm,
25 there could be some cross-ins.

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1 This gets to, if I don't call it a flaw, a risk
2 of accelerated approval and it's been acknowledged here.

3 If you have an accelerated approval, does this truly
4 compromise your ability to answer the question of
5 interest. If it does, then I don't think the accelerated
6 approval is acceptable because I think we need to get
7 the answers here for the full approval.

8 On the other hand if the judgment is this is
9 late enough in the process that any crossing in or lack
10 of adherence to the control intervention would only in
11 a minor way dilute this assessment, then I would consider
12 it to be acceptable.

13 I'll just note here I acknowledge my NCI
14 colleagues as they point out the ethical dilemmas. I've
15 had this ethical dilemma for a long time as we've
16 implemented accelerated approval in HIV settings and
17 oncology settings.

18 Is it ethical to say I have enough evidence
19 to bring forth to regulatory authorities approval of a
20 new intervention and, yet, I'm still going to enter or
21 follow people in a controlled trial to be able to get
22 at what we recognize to be the ultimate answer that we
23 know we have to get. That's a dilemma that I think all
24 of us have to face.

25 But if in our judgement it is ethical, and we

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1 can adequately maintain adherence, then I think it is
2 appropriate to consider this accelerated approval and
3 this strategy so long as we're insured that this six to
4 seven-year answer is going to be achievable.

5 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Fleming.

6 Dr. Sheets.

7 DR. SHEETS: Can I say I agree with everything
8 you said?

9 DR. FLEMING: You sure can. The committee
10 would be grateful and so would everyone else.

11 DR. SHEETS: I find the constraint in the
12 argument of Dr. Fleming to be the ethical consideration
13 of early termination or accelerated approval. Although
14 the trial that he outlines and others have outlined ahead
15 of him is probably doable, I think you would get to the
16 point where clinically speaking it would be very difficult
17 to continue on with the placebo arm.

18 I believe that the endpoint is CIN 2/3, although
19 I would caution that we should continue to collect data
20 on cytology, as was pointed out previously, because we
21 are assuming here that colposcopy as the gold standard
22 has no downsides and that's not true by any means.

23 As much as we would like to say that we are
24 experts at this and we are perfect, we're not. The
25 sensitivity and specificity of colposcopy leaves

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1 something to be desired. I think we need to look at the
2 endpoint of a high-risk cytology and histology together.

3
4 People who have colposcopically negative yet
5 persistent high-grade abnormalities on PAP smears will
6 in excisional data have high-grade histology. We just
7 missed the lesion so we have to keep that in consideration
8 as we go forward with the trial that you might outline.

9 I would advocate also to approach, as has been
10 said before, high-risk women and try to endeavor to try
11 to keep these trials demographically representative of
12 what the future may be very soon in America and certainly
13 include high-risk groups within that not only in terms
14 of ethnic groups but socioeconomic groups that are at
15 greater risk for the development of high-grade precancer
16 and invasive disease with or without screen being present
17 in those communities.

18 I do think that safety data, as has been pointed
19 out before, is very important. Although we are using
20 recompetent material here that represents what is
21 probably exposed to a woman in general transvaginally,
22 we are giving it now systemically in certain a larger
23 dose than it has ever been inoculated into someone before
24 or vaccinated to someone before. I do think it's
25 important to continue on with rigorous safety controls

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1 in regards to these trials.

2 I'm not a clinical trialist and I won't tell
3 you how to do that, but I think it's important to bring
4 that data forward because in America although cervical
5 cancer continues to be persistent, we are not going to
6 impact on that cervical invasive rate, as has been pointed
7 out, for 10 to 20, maybe longer years. In the interim
8 the safety data is very important for these women who
9 have been given this vaccination.

10 That's all I have to say. I would vote for
11 only accelerated approval if it does not impact on the
12 placebo group for the CIN 2/3 outcome. In regards to
13 labeling, I think it might be premature but it would be
14 for the prevention of persistence of high-risk infection
15 and also CIN 2/3.

16 DR. DAUM: What was your interim endpoint?

17 DR. SHEETS: I would use CIN 2/3 as the interim
18 endpoint with persistence of viral high-risk oncogenic
19 type of analysis like Dr. Fleming has pointed out with
20 the final endpoint being CIN 2/3.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

22 Dr. Unger.

23 DR. UNGER: I think that this is a
24 nontraditional vaccine and probably for that reason I
25 think it's very important that we are cautious. For that

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1 reason I feel that this is our chance to really understand
2 what's happening with this virus in a natural history
3 setting so the studies have to be able to help us
4 understand what we're preventing.

5 I, therefore, feel that we need a CIN 2/3
6 histology as an endpoint. I agree that the study has
7 to be designed to help us understand what that CIN 2/3
8 endpoint means in terms of viral persistence of all the
9 types and immune response.

10 The trial does need to be conducted in
11 appropriate populations. I really don't see a public
12 health imperative to do an accelerated approval. The
13 package as far as what the recommendation would be, I
14 think that we only -- we have to stick with what we know
15 and what we've shown.

16 If we end up approving it based on prevention
17 of persistent infection, that's how it's labeled and we
18 can say what we think that means. Until we show something
19 else, I think it's ill-advised to label it as showing
20 something we haven't demonstrated.

21 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

22 Dr. Wilkinson.

23 DR. WILKINSON: First I would like to
24 congratulate all involved in this commendable meeting
25 on prevention of cervical neoplasia, a very important

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1 issue in women's health. I encourage accelerated
2 approval considering the evidence at hand and the
3 importance of the issue that we're dealing with.

4 I would favor an accelerated approval study
5 format with the CIN 1, CIN 2, or CIN 3 as the accelerated
6 interim and confirmatory points considering that CIN
7 lesion is the usual source of the HPV infection and that
8 CIN 3 lesions rarely regress. I would also make emphasis
9 that cytology and HPV testing need to be applied in this
10 process and safety net issues need to be addressed. Thank
11 you.

12 DR. DAUM: We thank you, sir.

13 Dr. Felix.

14 DR. FELIX: I will make first a comment. I
15 think one of the things that we saw presented were power
16 calculations. Eventually it won't make a difference
17 because if their studies are inappropriately powered they
18 will not reach statistical significance.

19 But I will say that the numbers that I've heard
20 in the power calculations look to me to be in error because
21 of the studies examining or the studies that were used
22 to determine that were lacking in taking into
23 consideration incident disease.

24 I think the preponderance of data on persistent
25 HPV is robust enough to use it as a primary endpoint.

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1 I think that a negative predictive value of nonpersistent
2 HPV is very robust for a prediction of CIN 2/3.

3 I would favor using that as an endpoint or a
4 co-endpoint. I would favor only accelerated approval
5 once. If for primary endpoint for accelerated approval,
6 I would chose persistent HPV at a minimum of one-year
7 interval.

8 But I would favor only granting accelerated
9 approval if FDA is aware that there is a complete
10 maturation of the data for the confirmatory process
11 already delivered, and that was very nicely stated would
12 reduce the interval by one year.

13 The secondary endpoint for the confirmatory
14 trial I would consider CIN 2/3 with a co-endpoint of
15 cytology because, again, we don't know what a vaccine
16 could potentially do to the reduction or change of
17 predicted ability of cytology once a patient has a reduced
18 inoculum. I hope that that data would come out.

19 As far as the labeling, for the preliminary
20 approval I would label it, if effective, a reduction of
21 HPV, a persistent infection by HPV that has been
22 associated with development of precursor cervical cancer
23 lesions and, if confirmed by the secondary endpoint, a
24 prevention of cervical cancer precursor lesions.

25 DR. DAUM: Thank you very kindly.

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1 Dr. Freeman.

2 DR. FREEMAN: I'd like to start with
3 complimenting the NIH, NCI, and the industry and many
4 others not here who have contributed so much to this
5 important problem of HPV.

6 After giving this careful consideration, I feel
7 that the traditional approach with CIN 2/3 as an endpoint
8 is the safest in this particular situation having been
9 involved and actually chaired the data monitoring
10 committee.

11 I understand the complexity of how data
12 monitoring committees can evaluate data and decide to
13 make decisions for early termination. It's not a trivial
14 matter and I would emphasize the data monitoring committee
15 needs to be an independent committee totally and the
16 principal investigator should not be involved in these
17 decisions.

18 The reason that I favor this as an endpoint
19 is this is an important decision here that will affect
20 many millions of lives. We don't know the outcome.

21 There have been randomized trials, and I can think
22 of one in particular recently in lung cancer where a
23 product was given to patients with lung cancer to try
24 to prevent secondary lung cancer where, in fact, it turned
25 out that the treatment was worse and more patients were

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1 dying in the treatment.

2 It was a subset of patients who continued to
3 smoke as it turned out. It was very, very good
4 preliminary lab data and clinical data to support this
5 clinical trial. But that is one of the reasons I think
6 that we need to be especially cautious with a study that
7 can impact so much on patients' safety and their outcome.

8 However, I would say that the virologic,
9 immunologic studies are very important and other studies.

10 For example, we talk about mucosal immunity and factors
11 in the vagina that could impact on infection.

12 For example, women in certain countries are
13 prone to use vaginal medications more frequently than
14 in others. Particularly if you're doing a study in
15 different locations, these factors could possibly impact
16 on the infection. We need to study these as well as part
17 of the design of the clinical trials.

18 I would use the CIN 2/3 as an endpoint that
19 both men and women will understand who will be receiving
20 the vaccine. Eventually men possibly in other trials.

21 Also that the physicians that have to take care of these
22 patients will understand the significance of the trial
23 and the endpoints.

24 Also I am concerned that if you give an
25 accelerated approval, the information that's on the label

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1 may very well influence what happens to the definitive
2 trial.

3 Obviously informed consents would have to be
4 changed based on that your control arms may be affected,
5 particularly if patients have not been fully entered and
6 followed for enough time. The definitive answers here,
7 or the most proximal answers to the real question which
8 is whether the vaccine actually prevents cancer may never
9 come to us. I think that is particularly important.

10 DR. DAUM: Thank you very kindly.

11 DR. GREENE: Thank you. A few comments. One
12 is the idea that even a perfectly effective and perfectly
13 administered vaccine could possibly eliminate all
14 cervical cancer is somewhat naive. I would say it's
15 comparable to expecting the elimination of cigarette
16 smoking to eliminate all lung cancer. Nonetheless, it
17 would be desirable if no one ever smoked cigarettes.
18 I think there is a certain analogy there.

19 Next is a question that came up earlier in the
20 discussion. What is the number we need to treat with
21 a vaccine in order to eliminate one case of cancer? The
22 number needed to treat, of course, is one over the absolute
23 risk reduction.

24 In this case we don't know what the absolute
25 risk reduction is so that we can't a priori calculate

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1 what the number needed to treat is. It may be that this
2 kind of a trial might help to give us some notion as to
3 what the number needed to treat is.

4 But it should be fair to people interested in
5 vaccines that the number needed to treat could be very
6 large to avoid one very serious outcome. Certainly
7 that's true for hepatitis B.

8 It would be true for the number needed to treat
9 with varicella vaccines to avoid one death from varicella
10 pneumonia so that a very high number needed to treat I
11 think would still be an acceptable indication for vaccine.

12 Next is that to me the most important point
13 that we don't understand yet is the durability of a vaccine
14 affect and this has very important implications in terms
15 of who and when you would suggest to receive the vaccine.

16 Who should the recipients of the vaccine be?

17 In theory, if the immunity was life long, then
18 the appropriate recipients would be children at birth
19 because that way you could be 100 percent confident that
20 all persons would be protected at the time of first
21 intercourse.

22 However, if the vaccine effect wans after 10
23 years, you would wind up with no net reduction in the
24 incidence of infection so that we definitely need to know
25 what the duration of the effect is in order to know who

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1 to treat with the vaccine.

2 The question of identifying "high-risk
3 population" is extremely difficult. Women who are
4 celibate life long basically do not get cervical cancer.

5 Everyone else is "at higher risk."

6 Among those people you can identify people who
7 are even at further greater risk on the basis of age at
8 first intercourse and total life time number of partners.

9 Women, for example, who are commercial sex workers have
10 ultimately the highest risk next maybe to persons who
11 are immunosuppressed, HIV, transplant recipients, etc.

12
13 It would be difficult for me to imagine asking
14 parents to bring in their girls for immunization if they
15 expected their daughters to have a very young age at first
16 intercourse or to have a very large number of sexual
17 partners life time. I would think that would pose some
18 difficulties. As the father of a 16-year-old daughter,
19 I'm particularly sensitive about this issue.

20 I'm not sure who we should label, how the
21 vaccine would be labeled in terms of who the vaccinees
22 should be and who should the targeted population be.

23 Finally, with respect to the definition of
24 persistent infection, it's quite clear from the data that
25 is already available in the literature, Woodman's paper

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1 and Lancet, Hoe and Burk's paper in the New England Journal
2 of Medicine that two cultures separated by less than 12
3 months really describe only incident infection and not
4 persistent infection.

5 Not cultures but PCR assays so that you would
6 need -- it would seem to me that you would need to have
7 two positive assays at least a year apart to define a
8 persistent infection.

9 Finally, I am persuaded by the discussions that
10 I've heard from the past two days as well as Dr.
11 Goldenthal's assessment that the difference between
12 accelerated approval and final approval might be 12
13 months.

14 I am persuaded from that, as well as the
15 difficulties that have been acknowledged with attempting
16 to complete a definitive trial in the wake of an
17 accelerated approval, that the accelerated approval
18 mechanism is not appropriate for this vaccine. My
19 recommendation would be that the standard approval
20 mechanism be used and that the endpoint be CIN 2/3.

21 DR. DAUM: And I thank you for your very cogent
22 comments.

23 Dr. Pagliusi, please.

24 DR. PAGLIUSI: I'd like to thank the FDA for
25 the opportunity to participate in this meeting first.

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1 Secondly, I would like to express our respect
2 to all the scientific community who worked on the
3 development of these vaccines and brought this field so
4 far.

5 Now, at this stage we believe that cervical
6 cancer is not a visible endpoint and that an intermediate
7 endpoint should be considered. We would favor CIN 2 and
8 3 as the most appropriate endpoint. However,
9 if trials should take longer than expected, infection
10 at endpoint would be a surrogate endpoint to consider
11 only if a sustained protection is proven because from
12 the public health point of view, a vaccine that should
13 be boosted every year or every second year would be a
14 challenge for coverage and compliance and may not be
15 useful at all.

16 In this sense the laboratory wishes to
17 accelerate the vaccine development and consistent with
18 this line we would welcome the accelerated approval but
19 provided that robust data is created to support long-term
20 duration of protection and that the persistent infection
21 is well correlated with CIN 2 and 3. We would favor the
22 one-year interval between PCR positive points.

23 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

24 As a penultament speaker, Dr. Decker.

25 DR. DECKER: This vaccine is an exciting

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1 prospect. This has been a fascinating discussion.
2 Prevention of ICC cervical carcinoma is a major public
3 health goal so the stakes are high, as are the penalties
4 for missed steps.

5 Based on our presentations and discussions,
6 I conclude that first there is not presently the necessary
7 proof regarding the effect on cervical carcinoma of
8 vaccine induced changes in virologic or cytologic
9 endpoints. As much as we think they're correlated, there
10 is clearly some uncertainty as to what the effect on ICC
11 would be are changes in those prior measures.

12 Secondly, a study endpoint of cervical
13 carcinoma itself is infeasible for multiple reasons.

14 Third, as CIN 1 is not a clearly defined
15 homogenous group, it's use as a study endpoint would be
16 problematic.

17 Fourth, it appears that the study using CIN
18 2/3 as the primary endpoint could be conducted within
19 time frames and expenses that are commensurate with other
20 modern vaccine efficacy trials.

21 Finally, my own observation, I believe that
22 licensure of a vaccine is likely to lead to widespread
23 use irrespective of license indication. This has
24 implications regarding the need for high confidence
25 regarding the outcome of confirmatory studies to reduce

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1 the risk that a widely used vaccine would later be shown
2 to be poorly effective.

3 At the same time, concern regarding the ability
4 to conduct these confirmatory studies, and moreover the
5 need for complete safety data in both males and females
6 before any licensure because it seems to me that any
7 rational use of such vaccine would target both males and
8 females such as we do with rubella vaccine.

9 Accordingly, I would recommend that the primary
10 endpoint should be efficacy against CIN 2/3. The study
11 should incorporate secondary or observational objectives
12 regarding virological and cytological outcomes so that
13 we can improve our understanding of the relationships
14 between these outcomes and CIN 2/3, and perhaps allow
15 for simpler studies subsequently.

16 Similarly with Dr. Katz, I would encourage the
17 inclusion of nested substudies to explore related
18 epidemiologic and clinical questions. The study design
19 should not be predicated on a plan for accelerated
20 approval but a design such as I have just described would
21 permit reconsideration of accelerated approval should
22 findings during the course of the study warrant that
23 reconsideration.

24 Finally, the license indication should be based
25 on the outcomes proven in the study which should also

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1 explain the basis for a belief that these outcomes are
2 relevant to the prevention of cervical carcinoma.

3 DR. DAUM: Thank you. To bring this
4 discussion to a close before I forget to say it, I would
5 like to really commend all members of the committee and
6 members of the sponsors who presented data to us and,
7 of course, our FDA colleagues.

8 I think this has been a very wonderful
9 discussion. I think the committee has transcended their
10 usual degree of excellence by having a very lively debate
11 and consideration of all points of view.

12 Having said that, I will very briefly give you
13 mine. I think that one of the things we haven't said
14 a lot about is that if we have a potential preventive
15 strategy to stop a disease like cancer that we ought to
16 do everything in our power to ensure -- I think everyone
17 in this room would agree with this -- to ensure that it
18 be developed to get the definitive answer of does it or
19 doesn't it prevent this horrible disease as quickly as
20 we possibly can.

21 Having said that, I favor an accelerated
22 approval strategy but only if things can be put into place
23 during that. First of all, what persuades me to be in
24 favor of it is Dr. Goldenthal's notion that we might be
25 able to get a confidently effective vaccine to the public

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1 a year earlier. I am sort of shooting for that.

2 It would have to be done predicated on something
3 in place to definitively answer the question about an
4 important endpoint. I agree with everybody else that
5 CIN 2/3 is a reasonable surrogate for the definitive
6 endpoint.

7 I think viral persistence were it to be shown
8 could be the interim endpoint. I don't know what the
9 exact definition is. We've heard many different attempts
10 at it. For lack of a better one, I think I would accept
11 the one-year cut off as a definition of viral persistence.

12 I would not favor interim approval if it
13 compromised gathering of appropriate safety data, or if
14 in the views of the people responsible for the study design
15 compromise the integrity of the study to get to the
16 definitive endpoint.

17 In that circumstance I would rather let the
18 year pass because I would not want uncertainty or erosion
19 of public confidence once it was decided this vaccine
20 were good enough for general public use.

21 I, like others, have commented, particularly
22 on this side of the table, am very excited about what
23 I've heard here in terms of a prospect of getting a
24 preventive measure like this out. I would like to
25 encourage everybody who is working on this problem to

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1 move things forward as fast as they possibly can.

2 I think that brings this discussion to a
3 conclusion. Before anybody moves, there are two items
4 of importance to deal with. One is we have a minor and
5 very quick presentation to make. It will take about 10
6 or 15 seconds to walk the presentation over. Another
7 two or three to gather it.

8 This is your moment in the sun here, Ms. Cherry.

9 Nancy, on behalf of the agency, the committee, and I
10 think really everybody else in this room if I could just
11 extrapolate for a moment, there is only one Nancy Cherry,
12 folks, in this universe and she cannot be replaced and
13 will be missed sorely. Thank you so much.

14 MS. CHERRY: Thanks to all of you. I was going
15 to wait until the end of the closed session today to say
16 goodbye to my committee because it's been such an honor
17 and a privilege to work with them. Those are hackneyed
18 words, I know, but I really, really mean them.

19 I've taken this job probably more
20 seriously than I should have and more personally than
21 I should have and I've never gotten over my feeling that
22 a kid would have of being totally awed by the group I'm
23 working with. Not just your reputations, not just the
24 importance of what you're doing, but also how good the
25 people are. How good all of you are.

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1 It took a lot of thinking to decide when to
2 announce that I was ready to retire and you all are
3 certainly making it difficult today.

4 DR. DAUM: Maybe you'll reconsider.

5 MS. CHERRY: Thank you all.

6 DR. DAUM: Now, before everyone starts milling
7 around, I would like to briefly take a line of demarcation
8 here from Dr. Goldberg over and just ask the troops whether
9 you would like to break for lunch or whether you would
10 like to continue working through. Break for lunch? Work
11 through? Okay. We will then take a 10-minute pause,
12 let the room clear, potty break, etc., and we'll
13 reassemble with the review of the lab.

14 (Whereupon, at 12:24 p.m. off the record until
15 12:43 p.m.)

16 DR. DAUM: Okay. Welcome back everyone,
17 committee members, FDA folks. This is an open session
18 on the briefing on activities in the Laboratory of
19 Bacterial Toxins. We are going to try and complete this
20 in a succinct but thorough style and begin by calling
21 on Dr. Walker.

22 Did I see him? There he is. Thank you, Dr.
23 Walker. Welcome. He will talk to us about the
24 organizational structure and overview of research and
25 regulatory responsibilities in the Division of Bacterial

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1 Parasitic and Allergenic Products.

2 Dr. Walker.

3 DR. WALKER: Thank you. Good afternoon.
4 Hopefully everybody can hear me now.

5 In a few minutes you're going to hear
6 presentations of the research of Dr. Vann and Dr. Schmitt.

7 For this reason I've been asked to give a little
8 introduction to their presentations by giving you an
9 overview of the Division of Bacterial, Parasitic, and
10 Allergenic Products.

11 I'll do that in two ways. First, I'll talk
12 about the functions of the division and then I'll talk
13 a little bit about the organization of the division to
14 meet these functions.

15 Very briefly, our mission of functions is to
16 assure safe and effective products for control of
17 bacterial, parasitic, and allergenic agents affecting
18 human health. This involves a number of activities by
19 the people in the division. One of those activities is
20 research. The other is review.

21 Something I might mention about putting these
22 two together, it's sometimes hard for these people to
23 manage their schedules because things coming in for review
24 are not always something that somebody can plan for so
25 this creates a scheduling problem. As you'll see when

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1 you hear the presentations this afternoon, these people
2 do get the work done anyway.

3 In addition to the review, there's
4 post-licensure surveillance with the things that it
5 involves like inspections, log-release testing, and
6 review of label and promotional activities. Then we
7 continue to consult with outside organizations like WHO
8 and others that are dealing with problems that are
9 pertinent to the FDA.

10 I just want to show this to illustrate the
11 involvement of the FDA research and reviewers in the
12 lifetime of a product. As you can see here, the important
13 take-home message from this slide is not all the
14 individual components under each section of the
15 development of a product, but the fact that there's
16 activities that go on under each section of the
17 development of the product.

18 Like here in very early stages meeting with
19 sponsors, providing some guidance, review of original
20 submission and subsequent amendments, technical advice
21 for product and assay development, review of product
22 manufacturing data, determination of product specs, and,
23 of course, continued discussion with sponsors.

24 I don't want to belabor this since we're moving
25 along with regards to time but, as you can see, after

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1 license activities there is present the product to the
2 advisory committee, continue to have dialogue with the
3 sponsors, and continue to evaluate the products and review
4 the procedures that are being used in manufacturing and
5 so forth.

6 The point, like I said, that comes out of this
7 is once a product is licensed, the story is not over.
8 The job continues. Post-licensure we still have to
9 review biological deviation reports from industry,
10 participate in inspection of licensed products, view
11 post-approval commitments, so forth. It's a long-term
12 ongoing process.

13 To make the challenge even greater in dealing
14 with all these products, there's a tremendous variety
15 of products that research and reviewers have to deal with.

16 You can see by looking at this figure about new and
17 improved products that might be possible in the next 10
18 years.

19 There are respiratory pathogens dealing all
20 the way from life-threatening diseases to those that cause
21 ear infections, sexually transmitted pathogens,
22 diarrhea-causing pathogens like campylobacter and so
23 forth, and other mucosally trafficking pathogens like
24 salmonella, heliobacter, and so forth.

25 There's quite a variety of pathogens, most of

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1 these mucosal pathogens that are shown on this slide.
2 Also we need to think about pathogens that are not
3 necessarily mucosal like those that are like materia,
4 lyme disease that are encountered by penetrating
5 inoculation.

6 And then something that is, of course, is very
7 relevant these days, special pathogens, biological
8 terrorism type agents like franciscella santhrasious,
9 clostridium botulinum, franciscella tularendous, and
10 arensia peskas.

11 In addition to these pathogens, we also have
12 products, the allergenic antigens dealing with latex
13 antigens, cockroach, and various plant antigens, and skin
14 test antigens. I'm just trying to give you the picture
15 that there is a variety of types of products that our
16 people have to be able to deal with over the next couple
17 of years.

18 To meet these challenges the Division of
19 Bacterial, Parasitic, and Allergenic Products is divided
20 into eight laboratories. There's the immediate Office
21 of the Director with myself. I have an excellent deputy
22 director Carolyn Deal.

23 Carolyn and I are supported by people who are
24 regulatory and administrative staffs. We work together
25 to help all these people in the various laboratories

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1 accomplish the jobs that they have to do.

2 We have eight laboratories. The Laboratory
3 of Respiratory and Special Pathogens, Laboratory of
4 Bacterial Toxins, which you'll be hearing from today,
5 Laboratory of Mycobacterial Diseases and Cellular
6 Immunology, Laboratory of Methods Development and Quality
7 Control, Laboratory of Immunobiochemistry which is
8 allergenic products, Laboratory of Biophysics,
9 Laboratory of Sexually Transmitted Diseases, and
10 Laboratory of Bacterial Polysaccharides.

11 If you look at these laboratory names, you'll
12 see that they are identified by the types of pathogens
13 and types of approaches they use. I think it is also
14 important to realize that the talents and the resources
15 that are present in these different laboratories we
16 brought together on certain focus areas.

17 These are some of the focus areas that we're
18 currently dealing with in our division. One of those
19 is standardization of assay methods for bacterial,
20 parasitic, and allergenic products. Also a large group
21 is focusing on pertussis and other toximediated diseases.

22 You'll hear a little bit of that in just a few minutes.

23 Mycobacterial and other intercellular parasites.

24 It was mentioned this morning how important
25 mucosal immunization is and how much we need to know about

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1 that. We've got work going studying mucosal pathogenesis
2 and immunization, products to combat bioterrorism. We
3 also have a very active group dealing with allogenic
4 products.

5 What I'm trying to show in this slide on the
6 screen now is that you can take those laboratories and
7 those focus areas and sort of think of it in terms of
8 a matrix. You can just see how we pull our resources
9 together to accomplish things.

10 All of the laboratory names are shown across
11 the top. I've abbreviated some of them just to make it
12 easier to read. The various focus programs are shown
13 going vertically.

14 If you look at assay standardization, that's
15 something that involves everybody, all the laboratories
16 to some degree or another. Pertussis and toxinmediated
17 diseases involves work from the Laboratory of Methods
18 Development and Quality Control, as well as biophysics,
19 toxins, and the respiratory and special pathogens groups.

20 Microbacteria is really one laboratory that's
21 dealing with that. Mucosal pathogenesis immunization,
22 one laboratory dealing with that. We now have six
23 laboratories out of the eight that are dealing with some
24 aspect of bioterrorism agents and two of the laboratories,
25 Biophysics and Laboratory of Immunobiochemistry, they

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1 are dealing with allergenic products.

2 I'm going to go very quickly through this.
3 I have identified these laboratories and this will just
4 give you a little bit of flavor of the type of research
5 that is going on. The Laboratory of Biophysics they use
6 various instrumentation such as NMR to characterize
7 biopolymers.

8 Examples are given here. And macromolecular
9 assemblies so they bring a lot of technology that really
10 opens up new doors for some of us in the other sections.

11 They also have computer or simulation methods for
12 collector myogen analysis.

13 Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins, we're not going
14 to say anything about that because you're going to be
15 hearing about their program in just a few minutes.
16 Laboratory of Respiratory and Special Pathogens conducts
17 structure and fluctuation studies of various toxins and
18 regulation of virulence factors, B. pertussis and B.
19 anthracis.

20 Laboratory of Bacterial Polysaccharides is
21 another rather large laboratory in our division. They
22 characterize immune responses to polysaccharide and
23 conjugate vaccines and work toward standardization of
24 methods for relevant clinical applications and develop
25 physical and chemical methods for improved evaluation

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1 of license and experimental vaccines. There's quite a
2 lot of work there to do with the polysaccharide and the
3 conjugate vaccines.

4 Mycobacterial Diseases and Cellular Immunology
5 are evaluating immune responses to intercellular
6 bacteria, mycobacteria and tuberculosis. They are
7 assessing vaccine strategies particularly for
8 tuberculosis.

9 Enterics is looking at pathogenic mechanisms
10 such as invasion mechanisms of campobacteria and
11 shigella, hormonal controls of conococcal pathogens,
12 mucosal immunity that will help us understand not only
13 these but other pathogens infecting mucosal services.

14 The Laboratory of Methods Development and
15 Quality Control, as the name suggest, is one set up to
16 develop, standardize, and evaluate quality control
17 methods for bacterial vaccines and develop and evaluate
18 and apply the serological methods to measure immune
19 responses in vaccine trials.

20 Also an aspect of the overall lab accreditation
21 project the FDA is doing now, people in this laboratory
22 help coordinate the quality assurance activities within
23 our division, provide leadership and initiative to
24 accredit to the CBER Quality Control Testing
25 Laboratories.

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1 The final laboratory I want to mention is
2 Laboratory of Immunobiochemistry where they are looking
3 at not only the allergen structure inflections but the
4 immune responses caused by these allergens, as well as
5 ways to modulate these immune responses.

6 As you can see, we have a variety of things
7 going on. We have a lot of talented people. In just
8 a couple of minutes you'll hear from two of them and have
9 a better appreciation for what they are doing. Thank
10 you.

11 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Walker.
12 Are there any comments or questions, concerns? Thank
13 you again. I appreciate your time.

14 I would like to next introduce Dr. Willie Vann
15 in one of two hats that he'll be wearing in the next little
16 while. This hat is as the Director of the Laboratory
17 of Bacterial Toxins, one of the laboratories that Dr.
18 Walker mentioned.

19 When Dr. Vann has concluded his remarks as
20 director of the laboratory, he will then transform into
21 Dr. Vann in charge of his program and tell us a little
22 bit about that. We'll actually have a hiatus in between
23 for committee comment if there is.

24 Dr. Vann, as director of the laboratory tell
25 us what's going on.

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1 DR. VANN: The Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins
2 is organized into three sections, Neurotoxin Section,
3 Glycobiology Section, and Corynebacteria Section with
4 three PIs. I'm currently the acting PI for the Neurotoxin
5 Section. We have recently since our review completed
6 the hiring of a new PI, Dr. James Keller for the Neurotoxin
7 Section.

8 This section currently has two post-doctoral
9 fellows and a biologist. They work primarily on
10 clostridial neurotoxins botulinum and tetanus. The
11 Glycobiology Section has currently a post-doctoral fellow
12 and a biologist.

13 This post-doctoral fellow is working on an
14 anti-bioterrorism project with anthrax. The
15 Corynebacteria Section currently has a post-doctoral
16 fellow and a microbiologist, newly hired microbiologist
17 technician. This post-doctoral fellow is also working
18 on an anti-bioterrorism anthrax project.

19 The laboratory has product responsibilities
20 for bacterial toxoid vaccines against botulism,
21 diphtheria, and tetanus, vaccines containing toxoids as
22 components of polysaccharide conjugate vaccines, and
23 botulinum toxins, active toxins, as therapeutics for
24 diseases involving muscle contractions.

25 Our review responsibilities include review of

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1 biological license applications, biological license
2 application supplements, and investigation of drug
3 applications relating to these above products.

4 In addition, we have responsibilities for
5 review of lot release protocols for botulinum toxin,
6 annual and prelicense inspections of manufacturing
7 establishments. We participate in efforts to monitor
8 and improve vaccine safety and potency. We evaluate
9 manufacturing deviations reported to CBER. In addition,
10 we provide expertise to the Office of Therapeutics on
11 glycoprotein therapeutics.

12 The FDA has an anti-bioterrorism initiative.

13 The Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins has incorporated into
14 its existing program research projects on bacillus
15 anthracis which are on polysaccharide biosynthesis and
16 iron metabolism.

17 The laboratory has organized to meet its
18 existing and future obligations. Existing toxoid
19 vaccines require a maintenance of expertise in C.
20 diphtheriae and neurotoxins. The therapeutic use of
21 plastritrial neurotoxins requires a clear understanding
22 of how these active toxins and not toxoids work.

23 Glycoconjugate and recominant vaccines require
24 expertise on molecularbiology and carbohydrates. CBER
25 has an expanded obligation in glycoprotein therapeutics.

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1 Thus, this requires a leveraging of expertise across
2 the center of which we are a part. We have integrated
3 into our existing programs an anti-bioterrorism effort.

4 The general research objectives of the
5 Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins want to determine the
6 function and structural basis for the potency of vaccines
7 and neurotoxins. Questions we're answering is, (1) what
8 determines the specificity of the interaction of a
9 neurotoxin with the nerve cells, (2) can we replace
10 expensive and low-precision in vivo assays with in vitro
11 assays that are based on biochemical measurements that
12 are functions of toxins?

13 A large part of our effort is to define new
14 targets for the control of viral bacteria. To this end
15 we are asking two questions. (1) What are the systems
16 for iron metabolism and *C. diptheriae*, an essential
17 component of virulence, (2) and how do bacteria make their
18 protective coats? Later you'll hear Dr. Smith talk about
19 his efforts in this area.

20 That concludes my summary of the organizational
21 laboratories.

22 Yes, sir?

23 DR. DAUM: Dr. Faggett, please.

24 DR. FAGGETT: I have just one question. I've
25 had a lot of action with botox injections and all that.

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1 Do you folks look at efficacy of botulinum toxin? Is
2 that part of your responsibility, too, or is it just the
3 basic science of it?

4 DR. VANN: We do review license applications.

5 We have the product lab for reviewing license
6 applications for botulinum toxin indications if that
7 answers your question. We also review IND submissions
8 for various indications using botulinum toxins.

9 DR. FAGGETT: So you would have information
10 on efficacy of toxin?

11 DR. VANN: Exactly. We are part of the
12 committee that -- we are part of the committee that
13 actually assesses the efficacy of the toxin for various
14 indications.

15 DR. FAGGETT: Of course, in D.C. we've had a
16 little experience with anthrax recently and I was
17 wondering are you also involved in development of the
18 anthrax vaccine or what is the relationship?

19 DR. VANN: The objective of our research on
20 anthrax is to actually develop targets for development
21 of vaccines against anthrax. For example, if there were
22 a key protein that we found on the surface of anthrax
23 or that was produced by anthrax involved in iron
24 metabolism, that could be developed by someone as a
25 potential vaccine.

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1 Or if there was something we found in our
2 research that was essentially for the survival of an
3 organism or the virulence of the organism, that would
4 provide information for someone to develop an antagonist
5 against the organism. This is lying foundation research
6 for the development of new things to combat anthrax.

7 DR. FAGGETT: Thank you very much.

8 DR. DAUM: Dr. Kohl, then Ms. Fisher.

9 DR. KOHL: Several questions. In the material
10 we got there is a little table on the funding of the
11 Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins.

12 DR. VANN: You're referring to the book?

13 DR. KOHL: I'm referring to the book from 1997
14 to 2001. Is that funding -- that does not include
15 personnel, I presume?

16 DR. VANN: The funding that I have listed there
17 does not include personnel.

18 DR. KOHL: Okay. So that is basically
19 research funding.

20 DR. VANN: That is research funding, yes, which
21 includes materials, services, and everything else that
22 is not personnel.

23 DR. KOHL: Okay. If you had to estimate what
24 the total budget is of the division, could you give me
25 an estimate for that counting personnel?

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1 DR. VANN: I didn't understand your question.

2 DR. KOHL: How much of the personnel work?

3 DR. VANN: I don't have an answer to that.

4 DR. KOHL: What percentage of your time is
5 regulatory? It looks like a lot but I would like to get
6 a feel for that. Who is primary involved in the
7 regulatory activities?

8 DR. VANN: Okay. That depends upon the
9 person. Dr. Schmitt and I, I would say, could spend up
10 to 50 percent of our time doing regulatory work.
11 Sometimes it's a little bit more. Sometimes a little
12 bit less. If you look at the organization chart, that
13 varies with some of the other people in there.

14 For example, the post-doctoral fellows, for
15 example, IRTA fellows who are post-doctoral fellows don't
16 spend any of their time on regulatory work. It depends
17 on the personnel.

18
19 DR. DAUM: Thank you. Ms. Fisher.

20 MS. FISHER: It looks like you have a very
21 important function, particularly now that anthrax has
22 been added. Your organizational chart looked very small
23 though to me. Do you have enough people in your
24 organization to fulfill all of the duties that you are
25 supposed to fulfill?

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1 DR. VANN: Thank you.

2 MS. FISHER: I mean, could you use more help
3 is what I'm saying?

4 DR. DAUM: What was that green stuff you guys
5 were exchanging?

6 DR. VANN: We do our best and we are always
7 trying to get additional resources to actually help.
8 Some things are beyond our control but we do the best
9 we can.

10 MS. FISHER: Well, I understand that. I guess
11 as a consumer I'm very concerned that you have adequate
12 resources and staff to fulfill the function that you have.

13 DR. DAUM: Dr. Deal, do you want to respond
14 to that?

15 DR. DEAL: Yeah. My name is Carolyn Deal.
16 One thing I think might be helpful to the committee is
17 to clarify that in addition to Dr. Vann's lab other
18 laboratories within the division also have a regulatory
19 responsibility for the anthrax vaccine.

20 In fact, his lab is not the primary one for
21 that vaccine's review work. That may be helpful in your
22 consideration of some of the workload of the regulatory
23 responsibility.

24 DR. VANN: Right. There's an entire division
25 that deals with the clinical aspects that are related

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1 to these things. What we are responsible for primarily
2 is product and things that are related to product but
3 that is still a lot of work.

4 DR. DAUM: Dr. Kim, please.

5 DR. KIM: You briefly indicated that CBER has
6 expanded to include glycoconjugate therapeutics. Can
7 you give me just a couple of examples of what they are?

8 DR. VANN: Yeah. One of the ones that is very
9 -- probably one of the ones that earns the most money
10 for biotech companies is monoclonal antibodies. One of
11 the first was TPA, erythropoietin just to name a few
12 examples. There are many others that I don't know
13 anything about.

14 The reason I actually am somewhat involved in
15 that is that I started out and my major expertise is in
16 carbohydrates.

17 DR. DAUM: Okay. I think we should move on
18 to the next presentation which will be by Dr. Willie Vann
19 where he will describe his own research activities and
20 his own research program.

21 Dr. Vann.

22 DR. VANN: For the sake of clarity of
23 presentation, I will discuss two of the research projects
24 in the research program. The other projects are actually
25 listed in the book.

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1 We are investigating the biosynthesis of
2 capsule of polysaccharides in our model system. We're
3 studying the biosynthesis of polysialic acid. Work has
4 been done largely by a post-doctoral fellow who is no
5 longer with us and a technician.

6 E. coli and nickeria meningitides which are
7 encapsulated with polysialic acid are generally
8 associated with invasive disease such as meningitis and
9 urinary tract infections. These are the structures of
10 the common known polysialic acid capsule of
11 polysaccharides. We are using in our system the E. coli
12 K-92 which is alternating 28/29 polymer.

13 As an added bonus to studying polysialic acid,
14 we also are studying polysialic acid metabolism.
15 Polysialic acid plays several roles in microbial
16 pathogenesis. The same system general pathway that is
17 used to synthesize polysialic acid is also important for
18 synthesizing other virulence factors for pathogens like
19 polysaccharide, capsule of polysaccharide, and the
20 eukariotic cell receptors for toxins and adhesives.

21 The genes that encode polysialic acid synthesis
22 are arranged in three regions. The central region,
23 Region 2, is specific for the polysaccharide. We have
24 concentrated our efforts on the understanding the
25 function of the genes that are in this region.

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1 Our approach has been to purify and
2 characterize enzymes encoded by the gene cluster and in
3 the process assign various genes to functions within the
4 pathway.

5 Our recent efforts have concentrated on the
6 polysialytransferase, the enzyme that actually
7 polymerizes the substrate CMP sialic acid into a
8 polymer and exports it through the cell surface. This
9 enzyme is a membrane bound enzyme and is characteristic
10 of glycosialytransferase and other pathogen bacteria.

11 What we would like to know under the question
12 of the mechanism of this enzyme is, one, how the reaction
13 is initiated, how the chain is elongated, what components
14 within that complex are responsible for initiation and
15 elongation, and how is this chain fidelity of the repeat
16 unit maintained?

17 We can summarize our findings thus far on the
18 elongation reaction here. The K92 polysialytransferase
19 itself cannot initiate synthesis, thus it requires other
20 components. It will elongate or use all of the polysialic
21 acids that we know as acceptors. It has a preference
22 for 208 link acceptors. It seems also to have a
23 preference for a hydrophobic aglycon.

24 We can use our current model to explain data
25 elongation or list it here in the next two slides. The

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1 first model proposes that there are three sites, an
2 acceptor site which binds the preferred alpha 2-8 acceptor
3 and two catalytic sites, one that forms a
4 2-8 linkage and one that forms a 2-9 linkage.

5 Once the 2-8 and 2-9 linkages are formed, the
6 newly formed 2-8 linkage moves to the preferred site and
7 then the reaction starts over again. The alternative
8 mechanism proposes that there is a 2-8 binding site and
9 a single catalytic site. Once the 2-9 linkages form,
10 the enzyme undergoes a conformational change to allow
11 it to bind the newly formed 2-9 linkage and then a 2-8
12 is formed and then you start over again.

13 We have approached the initiation reaction in
14 using two different types of methods. The question is
15 how many things are involved in initiating the reaction
16 and how does that occur.

17 One of these is using complementation. We know
18 that we can separate the initiation reaction from the
19 elongation reaction by simply cloning out the
20 polysialyltransferase gene. In the complementation
21 experiment what we've done is genetically add back various
22 components from the gene cluster and ask the question
23 can we restore the ability to initiate synthesis.

24 Another approach that we've taken is to try
25 to estimate the molecular weight of the complex that is

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1 actually doing the reaction. We've done this using a
2 method that is particularly suited for crude systems,
3 namely radiation target analysis. The size of the active
4 complex is inversely proportional to the amount of
5 radiation.

6 Our current model for the initiation reaction
7 is listed in this -- given in this slide. First of all,
8 what we've learned is that the initiation reaction and
9 the elongation reaction probably uses the same size
10 complex that consisting of a dimer of the
11 polysialyltransferase.

12 The complex actually transfers to some membrane
13 bound glycolipid acceptor. The groin chain stays
14 attached to the membrane acceptor. Now, what we believe
15 is that the acceptor is probably some glycolipid. The
16 next phase of our research involves understanding what
17 this glycolipid acceptor is.

18 Our efforts to do that will be to chemically
19 synthesis sialic acid analogs that get incorporated into
20 the membrane but terminate, and then selectively using
21 some of the newer chemistry to tag this acceptor and then
22 extract it and characterize it structurally.

23 The other project that we are studying is the
24 binding of tetanus toxoid C fragment to ganglioside.
25 This has largely been done by post-doctoral fellow Heather

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1 Loach, along with a graduate student in the Laboratory
2 of Biophysics.

3 Clostridial neurotoxins are very lethal and
4 they are produced by C botulinum and C. tetani. They
5 are the active agents in tetanus and botulism and they
6 chemically inactivate toxins or serve quite well as
7 vaccines.

8 We have mentioned before botulinum toxins are
9 a potential bioterrorism agent. However, botulinum
10 toxin is also a therapeutic for diseases involving severe
11 muscle contractions.

12 These toxins are organized structurally into
13 three domains, catalytic domain, central translocation
14 domain, and a receptor domain. The receptor domain is
15 the part that actually binds to the ganglioside on the
16 surface.

17 This domain is organized to be two domains
18 itself. One of those is elected jelly roll domain, and
19 the second is what we call a beta tree foil.

20 The binding of tetanus or botulinum toxin to
21 ganglioside is an essential first step in pathogenesis.

22 It binds to the nerve cell, gets internalized, and then
23 eventually goes and cleaves a snare protein that prevents
24 neurotransmitter release.

25 Most of the protective antibody to tetanus and

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1 botulinum toxin is against the binding domain. For that
2 reason scientists are currently developing recombinant
3 vaccines against the binding domain of botulinum and
4 tetanus toxin.

5 Our approach to determining the binding site
6 is to use available biochemical and crystallographic data
7 and then to make use of molecular model and to predict
8 likely binding sites. We then test these likely binding
9 sites by site directed mutagenesis and then look at the
10 binding properties of the resulting mutants, and then
11 in a reiterative process refine our model to hone in on
12 the binding site.

13 We use two types of molecular modeling
14 experiments to actually do this. The first is homology
15 modeling. In this type of experiment what we would do
16 is superimpose the three dimensional structure of
17 proteins that bind carbohydrates on the C fragment of
18 tetanus toxin and look for motifs.

19 Once we found and narrowed in on an area, we
20 then use our molecular docking which is based on the
21 crystal structure of the oligosaccharide and then dock
22 or look for energy at various locations of that
23 oligosaccharide on the three dimensional structure of
24 the C fragment.

25 Using that type of methodology we came up with

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1 two regions for mutagenesis. Both of these regions are
2 located on the beta tree foil section of the toxin. We
3 mutated all the residues here and what we found is that
4 one of these is actually essentially for binding. Thus,
5 we've concentrated on Region 1 as being the potential
6 binding site to ganglioside.

7 We later went back and did further modeling
8 using this docking methodology and identified two other
9 residues here, histamine 1271 and aspartic acid 1222.
10 We mutated those, did binding studies. In these traces
11 which illustrate the extent of binding, both of these
12 indeed are involved in the binding of the ganglioside
13 to the C fragment.

14 Thus, we've refined our model here and thus
15 far we have defined the binding site on to tetanus C
16 fragment as including these residues, the histamine and
17 the aspartic acid I mentioned before, the tryptofane 1289.

18 During the process of this research these residues were
19 identified in literature.

20 In the future what we would like to do is refine
21 our model using experiments based on the entire
22 ganglioside since most of these experiments were done
23 with a fragment of the ganglioside. We would like to
24 determine the effective side chain characteristics on
25 the kinetics and thermodynamics of binding. It

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1 determined the effect of these mutants on binding to nerve
2 cells.

3 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr. Vann. Do
4 we have committee questions or comments?

5 Dr. Griffin, please.

6 DR. GRIFFIN: This is probably totally obvious
7 to anybody who is a bacteriologist, which is not me.
8 The polysaccharide glycosialytransferase that you are
9 studying, I assume that they are involved with developing
10 the capsules of these E. coli and are important for
11 virulence of these particular organisms and are
12 potentially targets or something like that?

13 DR. VANN: That is exactly right. These
14 glycosialytransferase are the enzymes that actually make
15 the polymer. They are part of the machinery that make
16 the polymer and export it and put it on the cell surface.

17 More specifically, if glycosialytransferase
18 is negative mutants of bacteria, encapsulated bacteria
19 are a capsular.

20 DR. GRIFFIN: And are then less virulent?

21 DR. VANN: And are then either not virulent
22 or less virulent. In strains where capsule is essential,
23 they are not viral.

24 DR. DAUM: Pneumococcus for example?

25 DR. VANN: Pneumococcus, for example, has been

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1 shown with E. coli K1.

2 DR. DAUM: Dr. Kim.

3 DR. KIM: I guess one question, I don't know,
4 you may have that on your slide, do you cross-complement
5 between K1 and K12 glycosialytransferase?

6 DR. VANN: We've never tried that.

7 DR. KIM: K12?

8 DR. VANN: No. What we can do is we can
9 cross-complement it between K5 which is a totally
10 different polymer and certain regions of that genome.

11 DR. KIM: My question is if you have a K1
12 mutants what happens if you complement with the K12
13 glycosialytransferase?

14 DR. VANN: With K12?

15 DR. KIM: K92. I'm sorry.

16 DR. VANN: K92. Oh, okay. That's a different
17 story. K92 and K1 polycosialytransferase are
18 interchangeable. In fact, that's the way we do the
19 experiments. We do the experiments using mutants of K1
20 since most of the mutants have been made with K1. What
21 we do is we take K92 glycosialytransferase gene and put
22 it into K1 to study the system.

23 DR. DAUM: Dr. Palese, please.

24 DR. PALESE: Which laboratories are sort of
25 competing in your field?

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1 DR. VANN: Which laboratories out in the rest
2 of the world?

3 DR. PALESE: In the rest of the world, yes.

4 DR. VANN: There are a number of them. One,
5 Dr. Vemmer at the University of Illinois in Urbana. Dr.
6 Silver who is also a collaborator but he is also somewhat
7 competition. Dr. Troy who is --

8 DR. PALESE: Where is Silver located?

9 DR. VANN: University of Rochester. There is
10 Dr. -- in the synthesis of polysialic acid, Dr. Stephens
11 was part of the advisory committee. Then in Germany Dr.
12 Frosch works on niceria. There are a number. And there
13 are a few that occasionally you see another paper pop
14 up with something on the system. There's Chew
15 Wong who is a synthetic chemist who actually did some
16 experiments directly on solid transfers which was
17 directly competition. Then there's a group in Taiwan.
18 I don't know whether they are still working on it. Does
19 that answer your question?

20 DR. PALESE: Yes.

21 DR. VANN: Okay.

22 DR. DAUM: All right. If there's no further
23 input -- there is further input. Dr. Snider.

24 DR. SNIDER: I wondered if you would just
25 briefly comment since there is a bit about the anthrax

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1 in your section what you're doing and what the objective
2 is and how that fits in to the rest of things that are
3 going on.

4 DR. VANN: You have to understand that these
5 anthrax projects are actually new projects. When we
6 wrote this, these projects were just getting started.
7 Briefly I can tell you what I'm doing and I can sort of
8 hint to what Dr. Schmitt is doing but he can answer that
9 question himself.

10 The fellow in my lab is looking at a group of
11 genes that were discovered on a virulence plasma for
12 bacillus anthracis which seemed to include how uranic
13 acid synthesis and how uranic acid has actually been
14 associated with other pathogenic bacteria such as Group
15 A scrapococcus.

16 The question is why is it there, what's it
17 doing. We are just in the beginning of characterizing
18 those genes to see whether they're functional, what those
19 gene products do, and then later ask questions like what
20 does it have to do with hurdles.

21 DR. SNIDER: Thank you.

22 DR. DAUM: Okay. If there are no further
23 questions, Dr. Vann, we thank you for both of your
24 presentations. We will now hear from Dr. Michael Schmitt
25 who is the Director of the Corynebacterium Laboratory

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1 and the overall structure of the laboratory of bacterial
2 toxins.

3 Dr. Schmitt, welcome. We need you to probably
4 adjust the microphone down. Talk right into it.

5 DR. SCHMITT: How is that?

6 DR. DAUM: That's fabulous. Thank you.

7 DR. SCHMITT: So what I would like to present
8 today is a very brief overview of my research program
9 in the Laboratory of Bacterial Toxins. The focus of my
10 research is the characterization of iron transport
11 systems in the corynebacterium and bacterium diphtheria
12 which is the causative agent of diphtheria.

13 While the incidents of diphtheria has declined
14 dramatically in recent decades in the United States and
15 in other developed countries primarily due to the
16 widespread use of the vaccine, a number of recent studies
17 have indicated that greater than 50 percent of the adult
18 population lacks adequate immunity to diphtheria and is
19 potentially susceptible to disease. This is primarily
20 due to waning immunity and failure to receive booster
21 doses of the vaccine as adults.

22 Now, the vaccine is in the activated form of
23 the diphtheria toxin known as toxoid and it is recommended
24 for adults every 10 years. Additionally, since the
25 vaccine is primarily directed against the toxin, it fails

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1 to eradicate the carrier state of the organism. Fully
2 vaccinated and healthy individuals can potentially be
3 carriers of highly virulent organisms and potentially
4 introduce these into susceptible populations.

5 Another alarming factor regarding diphtheria
6 was the recent epidemic in the newly independent states
7 of the former Soviet Union which occurred in the mid to
8 late 1990s.

9 This is the largest outbreak of diphtheria to
10 have occurred anywhere in the world in the last 40 years
11 and I think it illustrates the important point of how
12 quickly a disease like diphtheria can reemerge when we
13 fail to keep an adequate vaccination of the population
14 and also when there is a partial breakdown in the medical
15 infrastructure which had occurred at this time.

16 So the organism I study is corynebacterium
17 diphtheriae. It is a gram positive aerobic
18 nonsporulating bacteria. It is related to the
19 microbacterium in streptomyces, a group of organisms.
20 And it is the causative agent of diphtheria with the
21 primary virulence being diphtheria toxin which has been
22 extensively studied at the biochemical level. We
23 actually know quite a great deal about its structure and
24 function.

25 We also know a great deal about how the toxin

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1 is regulated which has been an interest of mine over the
2 years and, in fact, has been known for over 60 years that
3 the diphtheria toxin is regulated by the iron
4 concentration in the growth media.

5 In fact, the human host is generally believed
6 to be very limited for iron with regards to invading
7 bacterial pathogens and, in fact, this low iron
8 environment if the host is generally thought to be a signal
9 to activate certain virulence factors such as diphtheria
10 toxin.

11 The tox gene, which is the structural gene for
12 diphtheria toxin, is regulated at the transcriptional
13 level by DtxR, the diphtheria toxin repressor protein,
14 and iron when iron functions as an essential co-repressor
15 in this system.

16 When the organism is grown in a high iron
17 environment, iron will bind the DtxR causing it to undergo
18 a conformational shift which allows it to bind to a region
19 that overlaps the promoter for the tox gene, thus
20 inhibiting transcription and blocking production of
21 diphtheria toxin.

22 In a low iron environment, which is the
23 environment thought to exist where the bacteria colonizes
24 in the upper respiratory tract of humans, iron is not
25 available to bind to the DtxR and, therefore, DtxR cannot

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1 block transcription and transcription of toxin proceeds
2 and production of diphtheria toxin occurs.

3 So my primary research objectives are to
4 identify and characterize new virulence determinants and
5 C. diphtheriae whose expression is predicted to be
6 coordinately regulated with that of diphtheria toxin.
7 That is regulated by iron and presumably DtxR.

8 My primary emphasis has been looking at
9 heme-iron transport systems in C. diphtheriae.
10 Heme-iron transport systems or heme-iron utilization
11 systems have been well characterized in gram negative
12 bacterial pathogens where they have been shown to be
13 important virulence factors in many cases.

14 They have also been shown to be iron regulated
15 in a manner very similar to how the tox gene is regulated
16 in C. diphtheria. Some of my initial studies when I
17 arrived at the FDA was to demonstrate that C. diphtheria
18 could, indeed, use a variety of host compounds such as
19 heme and hemoglobin and transferrin as essential iron
20 sources.

21 However, the mechanism for how it used iron
22 from heme and hemoglobin was not known and this was one
23 of the projects that I initiated. I set out a strategy
24 to try to characterize this system.

25 So the strategy I followed was to initially

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1 isolate mutants in corynebacterium that were unable to
2 use heme and hemoglobin as iron sources. And to
3 complement these mutants with a plasma library carrying
4 C. diphtheria DNA, and that ultimately characterized the
5 genes and the products on these complimenting clones.
6 And also to look at the molecular mechanism of how some
7 of these genes might be regulated. Are they regulated
8 by iron like the tox gene.

9 So I isolated a number of mutants in
10 corynebacterium that were unable to use heme or hemoglobin
11 as iron sources and then proceeded to compliment these
12 mutants with a plasma clones carrying C. diphtheria DNA
13 and identified two distinct groups of clones, one
14 represented by placid PCD293 which carried a gene that
15 I term HmuO, and another group of clones represented by
16 PCD842 which carried a small operon of three genes which
17 I call HmuTU and V.

18 The product of the HmuO gene encoded heme
19 oxygenase which have been well characterized in ucariotic
20 systems but this was the first report of the heme oxygenase
21 in bacteria. What heme oxygenase do is they degrade heme
22 shown here, but the subsequent release of iron in a heme
23 breakdown product.

24 What we think HmuO is doing in the heme iron
25 utilization system is that it will act on the heme once

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1 it is traversed the cytoplasmic membrane breaking down
2 the heme and releasing the iron into the cytosol making
3 it available for the cell.

4 The other clone that I identified that could
5 complement some of these heme transport mutants encoded
6 three genes that appear to be organized in a single operon
7 termed HmuTU and V. These showed a high degree of
8 homology to heme transport systems that have been
9 identified in gram negative bacterial pathogens. We
10 think it has a similar role. Actually, we went on to
11 demonstrate that it had a similar role in C. diphtheria.

12 What I'm showing here is a model of what we
13 think is going on in C. diphtheria and possibly other
14 gram positive bacteria with regards to heme transport
15 and the utilization of heme as a iron source.

16 What we believe is at the HmuT protein, which
17 we showed was a lipo protein is anchored to the side of
18 plasmic membrane by means of a lipid moiety so it's
19 basically tethered to the cell and the remaining portion
20 of the protein which is exposed on the extracellular
21 surface is available to bind to heme or hemoglobin.

22 We then believe it delivers heme to a permease
23 complex located in the side of plasmic membrane which
24 is composed of HmuU and HmuV proteins. This facilitates
25 the transport of heme into the cytosol where then the

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1 HmuO protein, the heme oxygenase, can then act on the
2 heme breaking down the molecule and releasing the iron.

3 As I said at the outset, my interests were not
4 only to identify the components and proteins involved
5 in the transport utilization system, but also to
6 understand how some of them are regulated. Are they
7 coordinately expressed with the toxin.

8 In the process of sequencing the HmuO gene,
9 I identified overlapping the promoter region for the HmuO
10 gene. Just upstream of the actual coding region was a
11 sequence that showed a high degree of homology to the
12 consensus DtxR binding site which could indicate that
13 the HmuO may well be regulated by DtxR and possibly iron.

14 Subsequent studies, DNA footprinting and
15 various promoter fusion studies went on to show that HmuO
16 was indeed regulated by iron in DtxR in a manner very
17 similar to how the tox gene was regulated.

18 However, the regulatory system for HmuO proved to be more
19 complex than what was found at the tox promoter.

20 So in addition to regulation by DtxR and iron
21 which was very similar to how the tox gene was regulated.

22 We found an additional layer of regulation in that in
23 order to see any appreciable expression of the HmuO gene,
24 he heme source was required, either heme or hemoglobin.

25

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1 Not only was there repression by DtxR but the
2 promoter was also activated in the presence of a heme
3 source. This we found to be very interesting and unusual
4 since heme activated genes had not been previously
5 identified in bacteria.

6 Additional studies to try to identify what were
7 the factors involved in this heme activation went on to
8 show that this heme activation was mediated by a two
9 component signal transduction system in which one of the
10 components of the system was involved in sensing heme
11 at the cell surface and then transmitting this signal
12 to a second protein located in the cytosol which then
13 activated transcription of HmuO.

14 What I have shown here is pretty much a summary
15 slide of the heme transport and heme regulatory network
16 that we think goes on in *C. diphtheria*. The two component
17 system I just mentioned is composed of a sensor kinase
18 protein, which I have termed ChrS, which has at its end
19 terminus a number of transmembrane regions and some loop
20 regions that extend to the extracellular environment
21 which we believe are involved in the binding of heme.

22 Upon binding heme we believe a signal is
23 transmitted to the C. terminal portion of the protein
24 which contains a histidine kinase which becomes
25 phosphorylated on the binding of heme and then can

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1 transmit this phosphate group to the activator component
2 ChrA which upon being phosphorylated will undergo a
3 conformational change allowing it to bind upstream HmuO
4 promoter and activating transcription.

5 Now, in high iron environments this promoter
6 can still be repressed by DtxR. Optimal expression of
7 HmuO would occur in the presence of the heme source, either
8 heme or hemoglobin in a low-iron environment where DtxR
9 is no longer acting as a repressor on this promoter.

10 Optimal levels of HmuO would then be predicted
11 to be made under these conditions and then it would be
12 able to act on any heme being transported to this heme
13 transport system.

14 We now believe there is an alternate or second
15 heme transport system in *C. diphtheria* since site directed
16 mutations in the HmuT protein do not abolish the ability
17 of *C. diphtheria* to transport mutalized hemes and iron
18 source.

19 Regardless of which transport system is
20 bringing in heme, HmuO would act on this heme coming into
21 the cell breaking it down, releasing the iron, and making
22 the iron available to the cell in order for it to grow
23 in the low-iron environment of the respiratory track.

24 Some of my future aims are to identify this
25 alternate heme transport system in *C. diphtheria* and to

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1 develop improved mutagenesis methods for *C. diphtheria*.

2 There are very few molecular tools in this organism and
3 the development of improved mutagenesis methods for the
4 chromosome would greatly enhance our genetic analysis
5 of this organism.

6 I also intend on pursuing structure-function
7 cellular with the ChrS protein. This is the sensor kinase
8 for the two component system to understand the mechanism
9 by which it senses heme in the extracellular environment
10 and how it transmits this signal to the activator
11 component.

12 I would like to acknowledge some of the people
13 who helped me in this work. Post-doc Sue Drazek, Craig
14 Hammack, and Carrie Brickner who worked with me on this
15 diphtheria project. Collaborators on this project
16 include Angela Wilks at the University of Maryland and
17 Shelly Payne, University of Texas, John Fulkerson who
18 is currently a post-doc in my lab looking at iron transport
19 systems in *Bacillus anthracis*. Thank you.

20 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Schmitt.
21 Downloading a lot of information very quickly.

22 Committee questions? Comments?

23 DR. KIM: I guess one question I have what is
24 the current status of sequencing of genome of diphtheria?

25 DR. SCHMITT: That is actually an interesting

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1 question. It was in progress at the Sanger Institute
2 but actually logging on to the website last night I
3 discovered that they actually just completed the genome
4 of diphtheria.

5 DR. DAUM: Who did that?

6 DR. SCHMITT: Sanger Institute.

7 DR. DAUM: Is that public domain kind of
8 information?

9 DR. SCHMITT: Yes, it is. It's available.

10 DR. PALESE: Anthrax. How far is anthrax?

11 DR. SCHMITT: Very, very close. They are
12 still filling gaps so it's not entirely complete yet.

13 DR. PALESE: Who does that?

14 DR. SCHMITT: That's Tiger.

15 DR. DAUM: Dr. Kohl.

16 DR. KOHL: I'll ask you a lead question that
17 Dr. Vann already got. What would make your life more
18 productive in your lab? What do you need that you don't
19 have?

20 DR. SCHMITT: I'm in the process now of hiring
21 a new post-doc for my lab. I think certainly once I get
22 that person on board --

23 COURT REPORTER: Can you hear him?

24 DR. SCHMITT: I'm in the process now of hiring
25 a new post-doc for my lab. That certainly will make life

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1 easier once that person is on board. Other than that

2 --

3 DR. KOHL: Do you find within the constraints
4 of the FDA that you can collaborate with people who you
5 would like to collaborate with?

6 DR. SCHMITT: Right. Absolutely. I looked
7 at a number of collaborators here. Certainly some of
8 the important people in the field that I developed
9 collaborations with that have been very productive.

10 DR. DAUM: Thank you very much.

11 Ms. Fisher, did you have a comment?

12 MS. FISHER: I don't know if it's specifically
13 for you but any of the bioterrorism money -- the money
14 to fight bioterrorism that Congress is appropriating,
15 is any of that going to the FDA?

16 DR. SCHMITT: I believe so. I'm probably not
17 the most appropriate person to comment on that.

18 DR. DAUM: Let's call on Dr. Goldman to answer
19 that. I suspect we've already heard the answer.

20 DR. GOLDMAN: Yes, indeed, Dr. Fisher. In
21 fact, the FDA has received \$104 million to support
22 bioterrorism. They got it only about a week ago.

23 DR. DAUM: Thank you, Dr. Goldman. Thank you,
24 Ms. Fisher. I think at this point, thank you, Dr.
25 Schmitt. That brings to a conclusion our open session.

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1 We thank very much the speakers and participants in it.
2 I think we'll take a five-minute break to let the room
3 clear and then we'll go into closed session and try and
4 finish up.

5 (Whereupon, at 1:40 p.m. the open session was
6 adjourned.)

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